

PRECINCT

Preparedness and Resilience Enforcement for Critical Infrastructure Cascading Cyber-Physical Threats

D6.2 Dissemination, Networking and Communication Strategy

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CA	Consortium Agreement
CI	Critical Infrastructure
CIP	Critical Infrastructure Protection
CP-OPS	Operational Command Post
DCS	Dissemination, networking, and Communication Strategy
DMP	Data Management Plan
DT	Digital Twins
Dx.x	Deliverable x.x
EC	European Commission
ECSCI	European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KG	Knowledge Graph
LL	Living Labs
PEP	PRECINCT Ecosystem Platform
RI	Resilience Index
RMF	Resilience Methodological Framework

Abbreviation / Term	Description
SEESCA	Southeast Corporate Security Association
SEW	Stakeholder Engagement Workshop
SG	Serious Games
TX.X	Task X.X
WKSP	Workshop
WPx	Work Package x

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable, D6.2, describes the dissemination, networking and communication activities carried out during the 24-month PRECINCT project duration, from M1 to M24, within the T6.2 - PRECINCT Communication and Dissemination phases, part of WP6 - Capacity Building, Dissemination, Exploitation Strategy and Policy and Standardisation Recommendations. Unfolding in six sections, they define the objectives, target groups, channels, means and indicators for successful research project communication, networking and dissemination objectives.

T6.2 objectives were to deliver and implement the PRECINCT dissemination, networking, and communication strategy, promoting the objectives of the project, its progress, and results to a broad and relevant EU CI stakeholder interest group. Led by the Transferability Manager, VIAS, the strategy focused on internal and external communications. The central goal was to ensure efficient dissemination and communication activities during the project, support internal information sharing, all in line with a clear path to open-access outputs in the transferability strategy which has the community of EU CI stakeholders and interest groups as a principal target audience.

In the present report, a distinction between the communication strategy and activities (Chapter 4), and the Dissemination strategy and activities (Chapter 5) is made to facilitate the description of the plans implemented. A complete reporting of the activities (publications on social media, scientific publications/papers, media kit, events etc.) carried out and channels used, is provided with supportive illustrations. These activities are then summarized in an implementation roadmap provided in Chapter 6.

The communication and dissemination activities have followed the three phases of the project:

- Phase 1 includes activities linked to project promotion of the project and were mostly produced during the first 6 months of the project.
- Phase 2 focuses on the dissemination of the emerging findings and achievements. Direct stakeholder interaction is initiated. The interaction is carried out through meetings, events, and workshops.
- Phase 3 aims to disseminate the project results effectively through scientific publications, policy briefs and events.

Different communication channels have been selected to efficiently address the different target groups and to reach a broad audience to ensure effective community building and to spread the results of the PRECINCT project. Collaboration with other initiatives such as ECSCI Consortium and PREATORIAN, DYNABIC, STRATEGY, EU-CIP, AI4CYBER, EU-HYBNET and SUNRISE projects has contributed to achieve more engagement by attracting potential stakeholders. Partners participation was also a key requirement to maximize the impact and visibility of the PRECINCT's achievements, solutions, impacts, and innovation. VIAS, leader of T6.2 largely contributed to D6.2 and coordinated the contribution from key actors of the dissemination and communication activities, listed in sections 4.4 and 5.4, respectively.

2 Introduction

The present PRECINCT Dissemination, networking, and Communication Strategy (DCS) deliverable provides a report of the communication and dissemination strategy implemented during the project to contribute to the maximization of the project's impact and to establish a collaboration with existing initiatives working on Critical Infrastructures protection. To achieve these goals, this deliverable enumerates all the dissemination and communication activities executed by the Consortium, the tools and channels utilized, the stakeholders' categories targeted, and the Key Performances Indicators followed and achieved during the entire duration of the project.

The collection of the activities and the definition of the strategy was coordinated by VIAS, T6.2 leader. A first step was to identify the partners and their role in the dissemination and communication activities, along with their specific roles in other EU projects. Then, in order to address good communication and adequate messages, the stakeholder interest group and the broad audience was defined. And finally, the action plan determining the planning, tools and channels of communication, guidelines, and messages was distributed amongst the Consortium.

The dissemination and communication activities are intrinsically linked to the exploitation of the project activities and results (operated by T6.5, leader ICP). Efficient awareness and wide exposure of PRECINCT, its findings, societal challenges, and innovative technologies, will increase stakeholders' engagement with the projects and the partners beyond the project lifetime.

2.1 Mapping PRECINCT Outputs

Table 2-1: Adherence to PRECINCT's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

PRECINCT GA Component Title	PRECINCT GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D6.2 Dissemination Communication and Transferability	<i>Report on the dissemination and communication strategy and activities</i>		
TASKS			
<i>T6.2 Dissemination Communication and Transferability Activities</i>	<i>This task will deliver and implement the PRECINCT dissemination, networking, and communication strategy, promoting the objectives of the project, its progress, and results to a broad and relevant EU CI stakeholder interest group. Led by the Transferability Manager, the strategy</i>	<i>Chapter 5</i>	Chapter 5 Project approach to Dissemination and Communication provides the PRECINCT dissemination, networking, and communication strategy.

	<p><i>focuses on internal and external communications, and pays attention to evidencing broad dissemination and outreach activities.</i></p>		
	<p><i>The central goal is to ensure efficient dissemination and Communication activities during the project, support internal and external information sharing, all in line with a clear path to open access outputs in our transferability strategy which has EU CI stakeholders and interest groups as a principal target audience.</i></p>	<p><i>Chapters 5 and 6</i></p>	<p>Section 6.2 provides an overview of the <i>open access outputs in our transferability</i> strategy and how this aligns with EU CI stakeholders and interest groups as a principal target audience.</p>
	<p><i>The following are also planned during the duration of the project: PRECINCT website (M2) Social Media Channels (LinkedIn and Twitter channels M1) Material design for flyers, brochures and roll-up (M3) to be used at project events. A bi-annual newsletter in coordination with the project WP and Task leaders. 'PRECINCT innovation/ lesson' will start at M14 on the website Scheduled demonstration and training events in support of accelerating broad adoption</i></p>	<p><i>Chapters 5 and 6</i></p>	<p>Section 5.5.3 Social Media Channels Section 5.5.5 Flyers and Brochures Section 5.5.6 Newsletters Section 5.5.8.1 Innovation lesson</p>

Table 2-2 : Mapping PRECINCT Outputs

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

In order to achieve the objectives identified in the project GA and by the EC guidelines, the present report is structured in 4 main sections:

- **Chapter 3** – corresponds to the communication and dissemination task to promote the project, and the project’s timeline followed to disseminate and communicate, and the liaison activities implemented with peer projects.
- **Chapter 4** – schematizes the implementation roadmap of the communication and dissemination tasks implemented throughout the project.
- **Chapter 5** – identifies and lists the communication plan and activities implemented throughout the duration of the project to ensure efficient communication activities during the project.
- **Chapter 6** – identifies and lists the dissemination plan and activities put into action throughout the duration and after the completion of the project to share the project’s findings and results, the recommendations and open-source data.
- **Chapter 7** – provides the conclusion of the activities run in T6.2.

3 Dissemination and Communication Task

Lead by the transferability demonstrator (VIAS), the PRECINCT dissemination, networking, and communication strategy aims to promote the project's objectives, its progress, and findings to a broad and relevant EU CI stakeholders interest group. The defined strategy focuses on internal and external communications and pays attention to evidencing broad dissemination and outreach activities.

3.1 Project approach to Dissemination and Communication

The present Dissemination, networking and Communication Strategy (DCS) lists all planned dissemination and communication activities, tools and channels, and matches them with target stakeholders' categories and KPIs (key performance indicators). This Dissemination, networking and Communication Strategy is the reference framework on dissemination and communication strategy activities implemented throughout the duration of the project.

Work Package 6 (WP6) Capacity Building, Dissemination, Exploitation Strategy and Policy and Standardisation Recommendations as described in the PRECINCT Grant Agreement aims:

- 1) to ensure targeted information and awareness-raising activities.
- 2) to engage with multiple CI stakeholder audiences to see open outputs from the project used and exploited, including outreach with training professionals.
- 3) to liaise with relevant (current and previous) EU CI projects to achieve synergies.
- 4) to support and incentivize commercial exploitation for the project's industry partners.

PRECINCT dissemination and communication actions are intrinsically linked to the exploitation of the project's activities and results. Efficient publicity and wide exposure of PRECINCT and its achievements increased stakeholders' engagement with the PRECINCT initiative, and the use of PRECINCT results beyond the project's lifetime. Ultimately, communication and dissemination activities maximised PRECINCT's impact on relevant players.

The WP6 deliverable D6.2 is a Dissemination Communication and Transferability (R, PU, M24) (VIAS) report on the dissemination and communication strategy and activities that were used by the Consortium to ensure that the project results are made accessible to the appropriate target groups, at appropriate times, via appropriate methods, and that those who could contribute to the development, evaluation, uptake and exploitation of PRECINCT outcomes could be identified and encouraged to interact with the project on a regular basis. This DCS was a reference framework for defining appropriate actions and evaluating impact of communication and dissemination activities, and it was updated and adjusted as the project progressed.

3.2 Collaboration with peer projects

Liaison with related initiatives, specifically, with projects from the SU-INFRA-01 topic, was crucial for the project. The collaboration with European peer projects, such as SAURON (Ports), STOP-IT (Water), DEFENDER (Energy), SAFECARE (Hospitals), RESISTO (Communications), INFRASTRESS (Industrial Plants), SATIE (Transport – Airports), SAFETY4RAILS, IMPETUS (urban safety), 7SHIELD (Ground Segments of Space Systems) and ENSURESEC (e-commerce) were able to boost and maximize communication and dissemination of the project's results.

The PRECINCT project also joined the *European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures* (ECSCI). This collaboration enabled the PRECINCT project to take part in a series of events organized by ECSCI and to be part of its network. ECSCI aims "to create synergies and foster emerging disruptive solutions to security issues via cross-projects collaboration and innovation. Research activities will focus on how to protect critical infrastructures and services, highlighting the different approaches between the clustered projects and establishing tight and productive connections with closely related and complementary H2020 projects. To

promote the activities of the cluster, ECSCI will organize international conferences, and national or international workshops, involving both policy makers, industry and academic, practitioners, and representatives from the European Commission.”¹ (ECSCI website).

In practice, the collaborative and supporting communication and dissemination activities took place by co-hosting events and to participate as invited speakers to partners’ European projects (see details in section 5.6.10).

3.3 Ethics and Quality control

Communication and Dissemination materials containing potential confidential or sensitive data were first validated by the Ethics Panel. The table below provide an example of materials that went through ethical validation (source D8.7).

Table 3-1: List of materials validated by Ethics Panel.

Type	Title	Publication	Comment from Ethics Expert
Website	PRECINCT project website - Ljubljana ²	14.02.23	General comment: Whenever you have personal data in your marketing material (including names of people and photos where people can be identified – I have seen both in your documents), you need to make sure that these people are OK with it. They can either consent through specific forms, or as regards people within the project, normally their general consent with their employers etc to work on the project “covers” for these uses as well. But perhaps it does not, so best to make sure. Discrimination and other issues I do not expect to find, given the nature of the project, but, of course, these topics also need to draw your attention as well.
Press release	PRECINCT project press release: BlueConnect magazine, Vias (French & Dutch) Press release, PZA (Dutch) Press release, AKKA (English)	14.02.23	No comment, see general comment above.
Newsletter	PRECINCT newsletters #	14.02.23	No comment, see general comment above.
Flyer	PRECINCT project Brochure/ flyer	14.02.23	No comment, see general comment above.
Video	PRECINCT project Video	13.07.23	No comment, see general comment above.

¹ <https://www.finsec-project.eu/ecsci>

² Dedicated webpage on Ljubljana city website: <https://www.ljubljana.si/sl/moja-ljubljana/evropska-sredstva-za-ljubljano/projekt-precinct/>

3.4 Advocacy and Impact

With its user-centred approach, the innovative ecosystem and the societal challenges addressed, the project aimed to maximize knowledge and impact of CIs protection across EU cities. Bringing attention and awareness on the findings and learnings to the key stakeholders, the project advocates for potential changes in policies and/or legislations.

3.5 Project Timeline and activities timing

The PRECINCT project is a 24-month project, initiated in October 2021 and finalized in September 2023. The Dissemination and Communication are a set of activities which started at the beginning of the project (as from M1, October 2021), continued throughout the project duration with strong timing dependencies on availability of project outputs (at least, as from M12, October 2022) and the lifecycle of the four Living Labs, and will continue for a limited period after completion of the project (beyond M24, September 2023). Within the project duration, T6.2 activities provided dedicated support to the project lifecycle, following the tasks milestones and achievements, as given in Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1. Project Timeline

In terms of timing, the activities and key messages follow the project achievements and timeline: provided in Table 3-2:

Table 3-2. PRECINCT Communication and Dissemination phases

Phases	Objectives	Actions
Early stages	<p>"Who we are, what we do, how we do it."</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project is launched, communication activities will focus on creating awareness and notoriety around the project, its objectives and approaches. • Strategic opportunities for the stakeholders (better decision making, etc.) • Threat scenarios deployed are defined. 	<p>The community of the project and the LLs are set up. The players are identified. The scenarios scopes are defined.</p>
Middle stages	<p>"What and who we have identified and how we will proceed."</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cascading effects and interdependencies, Protection measures are defined. • Resources to support the prototype development and the RI. • The transferability process is initiated. • First dissemination activities are initiated sharing the emerging findings through training sessions and workshops. 	<p>Living Lab Operations are launched. The interdependencies and cascading effects and the protection measures are identified, the indicators for the RI are identified. Trainings sessions take place.</p>
Final stages	<p>"What we have learned and what we recommend."</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination and recommendations are shared. • More visibility is given to the project findings and learnings. • Exploitation strategies are identified. 	<p>Information and knowledge are shared amongst the stakeholders.</p>

4 Roadmap for Dissemination and Communication activities

To reach the dissemination and communication objectives previously defined in a timely and adequate manner, the following roadmap in Figure 4-1 was designed:

Figure 4-1: PRECINCT Dissemination and Communication Roadmap

5 Communication Strategy and actions

This section is dedicated to the communication plan and activities. It provides an overview of the objectives of the communication activities and tools, the target audience, the messages to address and the channels of communication.

5.1 Communication Objectives

With the objective to maximize the exploitation and the impact of the project, communication actions undertaken were intended to reach a wider, non-specialist target audience, including the media. By adopting a language that is more accessible to the general public, the communication activities aimed to reach a public that understands the ins and outs of the project as much as possible, and moreover the societal challenges it addresses.

The communication activities promoted PRECINCT project's concept, activities, findings and societal challenges towards the citizens, the civil society and the stakeholders from different private and public domains, from national and international entities. These stakeholders are identified in 5.2 below.

Unfolding into four major targets, the communication activities planned to:

- 1) Promote and raise public awareness and enhanced visibility to the project findings to a broad audience, at national and international levels, and to the participating Consortium members and research program(s).
- 2) Enhance the understanding of the cascading effects and interdependencies between CIs facing a cyber-physical threat.
- 3) Facilitate and support people using the project findings, supporting the positive impact of the project.
- 4) Work on creating immediate/short/medium term commercial impact (this last objective is concretized by the T6.3).

VIAS carried out the leadership of the project communication activities. VIAS set up the most appropriate mechanisms and tools for maximum visibility and impact ensuring that all partners contribute to communication activities and assessed the communication results by:

- (1) Setting up the communication planning process and the media
- (2) Identifying all the partners in the planning (and informing each of them per week on their task)
- (3) Defining the media and channels of communication
- (4) Providing guidelines on the communication message and best practices.

5.2 Communication target audience

The targeted stakeholders, from different sectors of expertise in relation to CIs protection, represented the different levels of decision-making process, and were from the local, national, and European level, as from private or public domain. This diversity in the audience is in line with the objectives of the dedicated user-centred methodology implemented in the project (the Living Lab methodology), in which the participation and awareness of the different domains of expertise is crucial (for more information, see D5.1).

Thus, content was addressed with a non-specialist language, via the communication activities of the project focusing on informing and promoting the societal challenges in the following stakeholder communities:

- Living Labs members and partners
- Citizens

- Civil society
- Local and national authorities and first responders
- Local and national CIs actors and operators
- National agencies
- National and European security institutes
- European research, innovation and technology agencies and networks
- National and European industry and technology providers
- National and European Academia and Research institutes

The different targeted stakeholders are schematized in Figure 5-1.

Figure 5-1: PRECINCT Stakeholders - Communication activities

5.3 Communication messages

The messages addressed to targeted stakeholders aimed at being easy-to-understand and responding to their needs and level of decision/action. A summarized description of these messages is provided in Table 5-1.

Table 5-1: Communication messages to the stakeholders

Audience	Message
Citizens	Societal values, impact on their own safety
First responders	Strategic and Societal values, tools functionalities, Cascading effects and CIs mapping
Crisis Management	Strategic and Societal values, data availability and frequency, tools functionalities, Cascading effects and Mitigation actions
Local agencies	Strategic, Economic and societal values, Information sharing on incidents, threats and vulnerabilities, Cascading effects and interdependencies, Resilience Index and indicators, Mitigation actions,
National/Regional Agencies	Strategic, Economic and societal values, Information sharing on incidents, threats and vulnerabilities, Cascading effects and interdependencies, Resilience Index and indicators, Mitigation actions,
European Agencies	Strategic, Economic and societal values, Information sharing on incidents, threats and vulnerabilities, Cascading effects and interdependencies, Resilience Index and indicators, Mitigation actions, Liaison activities
CIs and energy operators	Technologies and data used and available, Information sharing of incidents, threat and vulnerabilities.
Academia and Research Institutes	Technologies and transfer of knowledge, Users needs

To coordinate these targeted messages, VIAS identified the key messages to convey to the PRECINCT stakeholders, per Work Package. These messages are summarized in the Table 5-2 below.

Table 5-2: Communication messages per PRECINCT WP

Work Package	Key messages
WP1	CIs Interdependencies network and the cascading effects of a cyber-physical threat; Resilience Index methodology. CIs needs analysis
WP2	PRECINCT Ecosystem Operational Infrastructure PRECINCT Blueprints
WP3	Serious Games training objectives and values Stakeholders and first responders' training needs
WP4	CIs Identification and Mapping, Early warning system detection, first responders needs
WP5	User-centred approach with the Living Lab Methodology PEP components and its application in the fields of crisis management
WP6	Broad EU stakeholders' engagement General communication and awareness

5.4 Communication players

The communication players were internal and external of the project: the Consortium partners, the Advisory Board and the other European projects partner to PRECINCT (ECSCI Consortium, PREATORIAN, DYNABIC...). The following sections provide a description of the actions and roles of the partners Consortium. The communication activities provided during external meeting organized by partner projects are documented in Table 5-12: Conference participation

5.4.1 EOS

EOS, leader of WP6 activities, carried out the final responsibility of the visibility of the project and its results and the correct execution of the communication, dissemination and transferability plan. They executed the following activities:

- Contributed to the newsletters for WP6 and shared the newsletters once they were published.
- Organised 5 events aimed at engaging stakeholders and presenting to them the work done by PRECINCT.
- includes selecting a venue and date for the workshops; holding calls with partners to organise the content and purpose of the workshops; and gathering a list of relevant external participants to ensure the workshops have maximum impact.
- Promoted the social media channels of PRECINCT and populated them with posts regarding events or the project in general.
- Created a project [video](#).
- Created a [YouTube Channel](#) for PRECINCT and uploaded all of the recordings of the workshops to it.
- Presented PRECINCT at the ARES 2022 Conference and the Projects to Policy Seminar 2022.
- Created and shared the materials for the PRECINCT events (save the dates, invitations, roll-ups, flyers, name tags, booklets, etc.).
- Coordinated Communication and Dissemination activities within the project by hosting monthly WP6 meetings.
- Presented WP6 to the EC during the reviews.

5.4.2 VIAS

Within WP6, VIAS led T6.2, which consisted of the delivery and implementation of the PRECINCT dissemination, networking, and communication strategy. It was expected that within T6.2 all members of the Consortium played an active role in the execution of the communication strategy. VIAS had the task to motivate the partners in their active participation to maximize the results.

In addition, VIAS (partner #18) participated in T6.2 (with 5PM) as WP5 Living Lab Operation, Living Lab 2 Operation Antwerp (T5.4) and Transferability Demonstrator (T5.7) leader. This central role enabled VIAS to work in close collaboration with the stakeholders and the end-users in the LL, and the transferability demonstrators. Thanks to its notoriety as an independent and multi-disciplinary research institute, VIAS played a key role in supporting evidence-based policy making in Belgium which enabled VIAS to hold a long-established position with the authorities and police and security/safety forces. VIAS used its networks and research expertise to promote and disseminate the project's findings, innovative approach, and outputs, and to strengthen Belgium's international and national image of leadership and innovation in tackling emerging crisis.

Table 5-3: Key actions VIAS

Key actions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation to PRECINCT Stakeholder Workshops (1st and 2nd) (introduction to LL2 ambition and objectives, societal challenges of PRECINCT) and PRECINCT Events (May, 2023 and August, 2023). • Contribution to PRECINCT newsletter and social media (External) • Updates on the PRECINCT Website • Presentation of PRECINCT project and LL2 ambitions to ICS Security conference (June 2023) and ISPIM conference (June 2023) • Presentation of LL methodology and Societal ambition at PRECINCT event (external) • On site workshops at CP-OPS crisis management with the Crisis Management team of Antwerp city (Internal) (an example here) • Interviews with LL2 partners and CP-OPS disciplines (Internal) • Submission of a press release in an e-magazine dedicated to Police (BlueConnect) (External) • PRECINCT Living Lab 2 demonstration session with the CP-Ops disciplines and the crisis management of Antwerp city (Internal) • PRECINCT project, WP5 and LL2 activities on Social Media channels of VIAS (for example on the VIAS Institute LinkedIn page) and VIAS team members (External) • Presentation of WP5 activities (including T5.1 and T5.4 activities) to the November 2022 EC review.

5.4.3 UITP

UITP is a worldwide network that brings together all public transport stakeholders and all sustainable transport modes. It offers value to the PRECINCT Consortium, acting as a crucial link with the project Consortium and to the sustainable mobility sector. The goal is to promote the importance and drive action towards collaboration between Critical Infrastructure actors working to tackle cyber and physical threats.

UITP's role in Task 6.2 'Dissemination Communication and Transferability Activities' is primarily to share project information and encourage the exploitation of results from PRECINCT with UITP membership and the wider public transport network. For example, both the Security and the Cybersecurity Committee, which are two groups of public transport operators, authorities and industry providers who are working to improve, respectively, security and cybersecurity in transport networks.

UITP's main communication objectives are:

- Improve knowledge of safe, secure and sustainable public transport.

- Increase project visibility.
- Ensure the public transport perspective is well incorporated in the project’s results and deliverables.

To achieve these objectives, UITP communicated about project updates and materials to its networks, as well as involved key member contacts in the project. Through several events, UITP brought together public transport stakeholders so that their perspectives are incorporated into the discussions with PRECINCT. In June 2023, PRECINCT spoke during the UITP Global Public Transport Summit in Barcelona. The session called “Security of critical infrastructure and public transport: A strategic approach” highlighted the importance of collaborative and systemic multi-stakeholder approaches to critical infrastructure protection. The audience was made up of public transport operators, authorities and industry providers. Besides that, UITP has also communicated about the project via their global channels: the UITP website and social media channels (Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn).

Table 5-4: Key actions UITP

Date	Project action	Channel	URL
25/10/2021	Project information – Static content	Website	Link
26/10/2021	Launch of project	Website	Link
31/10/2021	Launch of project	EU Express -Newsletter	
14/04/2022	Stakeholder engagement workshop	Twitter	Link
22/05/2022	Project presentation	Physical meeting	
13/06/2022	News article with related projects, in coordination with UITP resilience campaign	Website	Link
13/06/2022	News article with related projects, in coordination with UITP resilience campaign	Twitter	Link
13/06/2022	News article with related projects, in coordination with UITP resilience campaign	LinkedIn	Link
26/08/2022	Save the date PRECINCT stakeholder engagement workshop	Twitter	Link
25/04/2023	PRECINCT conference promotion	Member newsletter	
05/05/2023	PRECINCT conference promotion	Twitter	Link
22/05/2023	Project activities at the UITP Summit event	Website	Link

5.4.4 INLECOM INNOVATION

Inlecom Innovation is an IT Consultancy and Solutions SME acting as the technical and Living Lab coordinator of LL3 (together with Konnecta). During the project lifetime, Inlecom presented the PRECINCT project and LL3 objectives during PRECINCT Stakeholder Workshops 1 and 2, as well as to LL3 stakeholders during LL3 workshops organized by each LL3 CI and described above. Furthermore, Inlecom conducted interviews with LL3 CIs personnel or key stakeholders as part of the research task of the project, as well as organized and moderated the three LL3 Demonstration virtual event with over 40 participants in total and with CIs stakeholders from different domains such as crisis manager, IT Engineers, Traffic Operation etc. Finally, Inlecom presented LL3’s first results at RISE-SD 2023 conference, as well as having a respective abstract submitted and accepted, co-authored with KEMEA. The final results of LL3 will incorporate the subsequent conference papers being prepared

by Inlecom and KEMEA. Inlecom also contributed to the project’s dissemination material produced, social media and academic publications being submitted or being prepared.

Table 5-5: Key actions INLECOM

INLECOM Key actions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation of LL3 CIs Stakeholders to PRECINCT Stakeholder Workshop and Conference (<i>Internal and External</i>) • Contribution to PRECINCT newsletter and social media (External) • Presentation of PRECINCT project and LL3 to 8ITS and RISE-SD2023 conferences (External) • On sight visit at Airport and Crisis Management workshop (Internal) • On sight visit at Road Operator Operation Centre workshop (Internal) • On sight visit at Metro Line 2-3 Operation Centre (Internal) • Interview with LL3 partners and different inside each organization (Internal) • Training to H3CIP platform (Internal) • Participation in the submission of 2 Conference Abstract and 1 conference paper (External) • PRECINCT Living Lab 3 demonstrations events (Internal) • PRECINCT LL3 partners Website and Social Media posts (External)

5.4.5 ICS

As a leader of Living Lab Ljubljana, ICS took care of the promotion of the project and its results in the Slovenian environment and in the wider region. They organized several meetings and debates within the framework of the Slovenian Corporate Security Association, which contains more than 100 companies and individuals in the field of corporate security. ICS also used the opportunity to present and promote the project at the international conference Days of Corporate Security. This is an annual event that brings together more than 250 experts in the field of corporate security and decision-makers, managers especially of critical infrastructure in the wider regional environment. They took care of the presentation of the project for the members of SEESCA (Southeast Corporate Security Association), which includes corporate security associations from Slovenia, Croatia, Serbia, Macedonia and Montenegro. ICS coordinated and, with the help of LL partners, organized meetings at all 5 operational centres in Ljubljana, where the project was presented.

Table 5-6: Key actions ICS

ICS Key actions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publication of two articles in the corporate security magazine, which was also promoted through ICS LinkedIn channel. • Publication of an article of PRECINCT project in a corporate security magazine. Author: Aljoša Kandžič, “Connection different CI sectors through EU project PRECINCT”, pages 56-58. • LinkedIn posts in all Precinct newsletters • Development of an ICS e-mail newsletter in which articles and all other content related to PRECINCT is promoted. • Promotion of the lecture from the Days of Corporate Security 2022 event through the ICS YouTube channel • Presentation of the project as part of the 13th International Conference "Days of Corporate Security", which took place from May 30 to June 1, 2022 (ICS in cooperation with VIAS) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Promotion of the project on the web page of the event and all other official releases ○ Lecture with the title “Preparedness and Resilience Enforcement for Critical Infrastructure Cascading Cyber-physical Threats and effects with focus on district or regional protection” (PRECINCT project and case of Living Lab Antwerp) together with Mrs. Shirley DELANNOY, VIAS Institute Belgium (Belgium) • Presentation of Living Lab Ljubljana as part of the 14th International Conference "Days of Corporate Security", which took place from 25th to 26th May 2023 (ICS in cooperation with AIT)

ICS Key actions

- Lecture with the title “Cascading Effects Analysis as Part of Critical Infrastructure Protection (case of LL Ljubljana in PRECINCT project)” with Dr Stefan SCHAUER and Dr Sandra KÖNIG, Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT) (Austria)
- Promotion of the project on the same event with organising exhibition space with the banner
- Organisation of a workshop on the same event for the LL partners and all other participants of the event
- Promotion of the project on the web page of the event and all other official releases
- Presentation of the PRECINCT project as part of the international corporate security event of the 8th SAMKB conference "Days of Corporate Security" in Belgrade, December 2, 2022
- Publication of the two articles about the PRECINCT project in the Corporate Security magazine.
 - Article with the title “[Pred vrati so novi raziskovalno tehnološki projekti v okviru perspektive HORIZON 2020](#)” with author Eva Čaleta
 - Article with the title “[POVEZOVANJE RAZLIČNIH KRITIČNIH INFRASTRUKTUR SKOZI PROJEKT PRECINCT](#)” with author Aljoša Kandžič

One of the partners of the LL1 has made a major contribution to the dissemination and communication activities: the Municipality of Ljubljana. At the City of Ljubljana (MOL), a wide range of dissemination activities for the PRECINCT project were conducted to use our effort and networks to disseminate as much as possible the achievements and learnings from PRECINCT project. To support these activities, at the project's inception, a City Project Group was formed with the aim to comprise various city departments and services critical to understanding and ensuring the protection of critical infrastructure (CI) and MOL response to cascading events. The involvement of these services in the project group also served as a means of disseminating project news among other city services. Besides, the Municipal Constabulary Department (Municipal Police), coordinator of MOL within PRECINCT, provided regular brief project updates to the City Council and the Mayor as part of reporting on EU projects taking place in the city.

Major external activities conducted mainly focus on:

- Creation of a dedicated sub-page on the City of Ljubljana's website: <https://www.ljubljana.si/sl/moja-ljubljana/evropska-sredstva-za-ljubljano/projekt-PRECINCT/>. This sub-page served as the central platform for regularly sharing updates and information about our project activities.
- Contribution to PRECINCT Newsletter #4: 'On the way to greater resilience of the critical infrastructure of the City of Ljubljana'. Content also shared on the city website.
- PRECINCT event Brussels on May 16-17, 2023.
- Days of Corporate Security conference in Brdo pri Kranj, Slovenia, on May 22-23, 2023.
- Days of Security Studies (June 13-14, 2023), with a presentation on the technological solutions of the PRECINCT project contributing to greater resilience of critical infrastructure in Ljubljana.
- Eurocrim 2023 conference in Florence, Italy (September 6-9, 2023), which hosted approximately 1800 participants, and the presentation 'With PRECINCT Solutions, Ljubljana is Taking Steps to Protect Itself and Manage Physical and Cyber Threats.
- The presentations provided by MOL were followed with great discussions, reflecting the importance of the topic discussed within the PRECINCT.
- Active participation to other PRECINCT project conferences and workshops online.
- Regarding the activities and events in which MOL participated, concise summaries were published on the Ljubljana website, which attracts an average of 8,500 daily visitors. Additionally, some of this content was shared on the PRECINCT's LinkedIn group.
- Part of the LL1 activities involved visits to the operational centres of various institutions in LL1. MOL organised the visit of Ljubljana Fire Brigade, a key player in responding to cascading events and an exemplar of operational excellence. A brief news article about this visit was published on the city's website.

5.4.6 CORTE

Throughout the project duration, CORTE regularly communicated information about PRECINCT to its members of more than 70 entities comprising of national transport authorities, transport associations and industry. As an international association gathering and coordinating expertise and best practices on issues connected to road safety and security at the European level, CORTE provided information regarding the progress of the project to the members through its regular Enforcement working group meetings. CORTE will also disseminate the final results of the project, in particular policy recommendations (D6.5) to its members.

CORTE also communicated the information about PRECINCT to the members of the Consortium implementing the HERON project (Horizon 2020, 2021-2025). HERON will develop an integrated automated system to perform maintenance of road infrastructure, consisting of an autonomous ground robotic vehicle that will be supported by autonomous drones. The project will be deploying sensors and scanners for 3D mapping will be used in addition to artificial intelligence toolkits to help coordinate road maintenance, with the goal to reduce accidents and maintenance costs, as well as to increase road network capacity and efficiency, thus contributing to the broader goal of protecting critical (road) infrastructure.

5.4.7 POLIS

POLIS's role in PRECINCT involves primarily raising awareness about the project's goals, objectives, and outcomes among its members (city and regional administrations), including civil servants, policymakers, urban planners, academics, and transport operators. POLIS made a consistent effort to keep its members informed about PRECINCT and -if possible- involved, both in capacity-building activities and policy dialogues.

Table 5-7: Key actions POLIS

POLIS Key actions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>1st Stakeholder's Engagement Workshop (05/05/2022)</u>: The event was showcased in a dedicated article on the POLIS webpage. • <u>POLIS Annual Conference 2022 (30/11/2022-01/12/2022)</u>: A conference stand for PRECINCT was reserved (Figure 5-2). The stand was staffed for the whole duration of the conference by at least one person (from POLIS and AKKODIS). The project's brochure (A4 format) and flyer and first 4 newsletters (A5 format) were printed (50 copies of each), with about half of them being distributed at the PRECINCT stand. The project was also communicated in a catered way that would appeal to city and regional administrations, through a custom-made A1 poster. Finally, some first contacts were established with the Cork City Council, which showed interest in the project. The participation of PRECINCT at the POLIS Annual Conference 2022 was also shared on LinkedIn. • <u>PRECINCT Conference (16/05/2023-17/05/2023)</u>: POLIS reached out to its members participating in the "Safety & Security" Working Group (WG), through an e-mail presenting the project, the conference, and the potential interesting aspects of the project to the members of the WG. POLIS also targeted with separate e-mails its city-members that are the locations of 3 out of the 4 Living Labs (LLs), those being Bologna, Ljubljana, and Antwerp. Finally, the Cork City Council, having already shown interest in the project, was also targeted. Unfortunately, none of the POLIS members was able to attend the conference. The event was also showcased in a dedicated article on the POLIS webpage and was also shared on POLIS's LinkedIn and Twitter. • <u>Abstract submission at the POLIS Annual Conference 2022 (30/11/2022-01/12/2022)</u>: An abstract (attached) was prepared by PRECINCT partner Fondazione ITL, showcasing the LL4-Bologna. POLIS reviewed the abstract, and despite the interesting content, it had to reject it, as it didn't match the content of any of the conference's sessions. • <u>Abstract submission at the 35th AESOP Annual Congress 2023</u>: POLIS prepared an abstract (attached) focusing on the Digital Twin aspects and the LL-related activities of PRECINCT, and more specifically, those of LL3-Athens. PRECINCT partners Inlecom, University College Dublin, ELLINIKO METRO, and KEMEA, also contributed to the draft. Unfortunately, the abstract was rejected, as non-compatible with any of the conference's sessions.

POLIS Key actions

- **Focus groups (Late August – Early September 2023):** POLIS is planning a series of 2 to 4 group online interviews, each with a group of 4 to 5 participants. The scope will be to present PRECINCT’s results to local and public transport officials and receive input on how the PRECINCT solutions could be upscaled in their domains (also feeding T6.5 Policy Recommendations).
- **PRECINCT workshop (Mid-September 2023):** POLIS is planning a one (or one-and-a-half) day workshop at its premises in Brussels (BE). The objective is to present PRECINCT’s results to POLIS members participating in the “Safety & Security” Working Group (WG). Subjects to be discussed include the types of threat most predominant in city infrastructures and the appropriate resilience strategies to address them, as well as to receive input on how the PRECINCT solutions could be upscaled in their domains (also feeding T6.5 Policy Recommendations). POLIS is also coordinating with EOS to see if this workshop could be combined and/or be part of the PRECINCT Final Conference.
- **PRECINCT Newsletter:** A newsletter article focusing on the Digital Twinning methods employed by PRECINCT and liaisons with other EU-funded projects where Digital Twinning methods are employed is under preparation by POLIS.

Figure 5-2: POLIS Annual Conference 2022 - Representation of PRECINCT project

The project external Advisory Board, including other European organizations with direct relation with critical infrastructure, also facilitated the communication of the project awareness by extending the PRECINCT community. And the liaison activities with related initiatives, especially projects from the SU-INFRA-01 topic, have established collaborations to boost and maximize the communication and dissemination of the project results.

5.5 Communication tools and activities

The following communication materials and tools were defined and selected to reach as many target audiences as possible who might be interested in PRECINCT. The social media channels were used to create organic posts about the status of the project, and thus primarily informed people already familiar with the project and the networks of the partners on new updates. The other communication channels, such as the articles in journals and the brochure used at events, aimed at targeting new audiences. A dissemination tracker was developed in which the input of the different partners was collected.

Table 5-8: Communication activities

Category	Activity	Channel
Online channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online visibility. • Promotion of project updates. • Collection of other PRECINCT material. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media platforms
Publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications about PRECINCT developed by project stakeholders. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Articles in general publications (e.g., magazines and journals) • Blogs • Press releases
Meetings and events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consortium and WP meetings. • Dedicated PRECINCT events organised by the Consortium. • Participation in third-party events. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical, hybrid and online meetings and events
Promotional material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotional material about PRECINCT accessible for both the Consortium and third parties 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital flyer and brochure

5.6 Communication materials

5.6.1 Logo and graphic identity, media kit

In order to give PRECINCT a corporate identity and to ensure that this identity remained the same in the communication activities of the different partners, an overall project design and template was developed in M1 by VIAS. A brand book was shared with the partners to structure the requirements of:

- The logo (colours and different sizes).
- Typeface (Calibri or Tahoma).
- Design elements (big circles with small strokes, big circles with tick strokes, full little circles and patterns).
- Photography (real and bright).

Together with the brand book, a toolkit was developed containing the PRECINCT logo in different formats, the logos of the partners and templates. Neither the toolkit nor the brand book were made public. Illustrations are provided in Annex V.

5.6.2 Online communication

5.6.2.1 Website

The website was created in M2, and the design followed the predetermined PRECINCT branding. It ensured that the overall project information and any updates were summarised and easily accessible for third parties. It contained the following information:

- A general presentation of the scope of the project and its (management) structure.
- An overview of the Consortium.
- A description of the four Living Labs.
- PRECINCT publication material (videos, articles, promotional material and newsletters).
- An overview of events organised by PRECINCT and third-party events.
- An overview of other projects in the European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures.
- A contact forms.

The website will remain active for three years after the project's closure.

5.6.2.2 Social Media Networks

PRECINCT is visible on the following social media networks:

- **X (ex-Twitter) (@PRECINCT_EU)**

The purpose of the X page of PRECINCT is to keep the stakeholders up to date with the progress of the project and with communication activities such as the newsletters and events. In Figure 5-3, photos from the IUTP Summit where PRECINCT partners were present.

Figure 5-3: PRECINCT on Twitter – Photos from the IUTP Summit

- **LinkedIn**

A private [group](#) was created to connect the partners and other stakeholders with each other and to allow the sharing of ideas and good practices between them. Figure 5-4 is a compilation of posts done by partners shared in the LinkedIn group:

- (a) Announcing the final event of PRECINCT,
- (b) About the Demonstration with the CP-OPS team in LL2,
- (c) Publication of KNT involvement on their LinkedIn page,
- (d) UCD publication and their role).

(a) **Jenny Rainbird** • 1er
Head of EU Projects Delivery
★ Administrateur • 17 min

The PRECINCT final event is underway! Looking forward to an interesting day of presentations and discussions !

(b) **Shirley Delannoy** • 1e
Researcher - Anthropologist
★ Beheerder • 1 mnd

The LL Antwerp held its training session yesterday with the CP-OPS representatives and the representatives of the city authorities. We're entering the final stretch of the project. Netx step: the Interactive Demo day on June 26th. Si ...meer weergeven

Vertaling weergeven

Shirley Delannoy • 1e
Researcher - Anthropologist
1 mnd • Bewerkt • 9

Today, the Antwerp Living Lab held its training session on the components of the PRECINCT Ecosystem Platform to prepare the Antwerp CP-OPS representatives for the demonstration and testing day that awaits them at the ...meer weergeven

Vertaling weergeven

(c) **Stéphane Kündig** • 1er
R&D Engineer at Konnecta Systems
6 mois

Konnecta Systems
507 abonnés
6 mois • 9

+ Suivre

The #PRECINCT #DigitalTwin instantiation process is advancing rapidly at the project Living Labs!
Konnecta Systems, serving as the Athens Living Lab technical partner, ...voir plus

Athens
precinct.info • Lecture de 1 min

14

J'aime **Commenter**

(d) **Meisam Gordan** • 1er
Postdoctoral Research Fellow at University College Dublin
1 an(s) • Modifié

#UCD is determined to make strong contributions to the #PRECINCT dissemination and communication.
Here comes WP3's specific role in the project! ...voir plus

WP3's role in PRECINCT • 1 page

dependent and cascading effects in CI networks for enhanced resilience and rapid recovery
Work Package 3 by University College Dublin (UCD)

Summary
EU Critical Infrastructures (CIs) are increasingly at risk from cyber-physical attacks and natural hazards. Research is underway focusing on the use of CIs to become more complex and managing the impacts of cascading effects and restoring normal operation in the event of major perturbations and hazards. The ultimate aim of the PRECINCT project is to develop a resilient, inherently and securely for a safe Europe. PRECINCT aims to connect private and public CI stakeholders in a geographical area to a common cyber-physical security management approach which will yield a protected Europe for citizens and infrastructures.

In Work Package 3, we are developing a Serious Game tool as an innovative stakeholder engagement approach in order to identify potential vulnerabilities of the CIs to cascading Cyber-Physical threats. To aid the data mining tool used for trend detection from game play records, results, which can be used to inform the maintenance, monitoring and quality control of the data to support integration with Digital Twin, including the change between the Serious Game and the Digital Twin, building on the PRECINCT response functions for the Serious Game, and the integration of the CI model developed in the PRECINCT Blueprints to describe the tools developed and to ease development and implementation.

SG Serious Game System Architecture
Serious Gaming has been receiving much attention in recent years and represents a simulated version of reality that can enable players an experiential decision-making and evaluate the results. Serious Gaming are considered as complex systems architecture in CI, as they can be used as a platform for a distributed using real data and concepts from UCD. However, the architecture of the Serious Game system is not yet defined and the Digital Twin, building on the PRECINCT response functions for the Serious Game, and the integration of the CI model developed in the PRECINCT Blueprints to describe the tools developed and to ease development and implementation.

DM Data Mining Framework
With rapid growth of database technology more data are collected. This means an interdisciplinary field bringing together techniques from machine learning, pattern mining, network analysis, and visualization to address the sheer volume of information generated from large data sets. The framework is designed to support the integration of the data mining framework into the PRECINCT ecosystem which includes numerous tools and integrations. The main objective of the Data Mining Framework is to provide a data mining framework for the integration of the Serious Game system into the PRECINCT ecosystem which includes numerous tools and integrations. The main objective of the Data Mining Framework is to provide a data mining framework for the integration of the Serious Game system into the PRECINCT ecosystem which includes numerous tools and integrations. The main objective of the Data Mining Framework is to provide a data mining framework for the integration of the Serious Game system into the PRECINCT ecosystem which includes numerous tools and integrations.

Integration with Digital Twin
A digital twin is one of the leading concepts associated to the fourth industrial revolution (IIoT) with significant benefits. It reduces the cycle time as well as operational costs, increasing the efficiency of engineering, improving the production, and decreasing the risks. The PRECINCT ecosystem which includes numerous tools and integrations. The main objective of the Data Mining Framework is to provide a data mining framework for the integration of the Serious Game system into the PRECINCT ecosystem which includes numerous tools and integrations. The main objective of the Data Mining Framework is to provide a data mining framework for the integration of the Serious Game system into the PRECINCT ecosystem which includes numerous tools and integrations.

Figure 5-4: PRECINCT on LinkedIn – Illustrations of different publications

- **YouTube**

The [YouTube channel](#) of PRECINCT stores the recordings of the training sessions, workshops and events and are publicly available (Figure 5-5).

Figure 5-5: PRECINCT on YouTube, screenshot of one of the videos displayed.

Besides the social media channels owned by the task leaders, the partners were also encouraged to share regular updates about their work within the project on their own social media channels. VIAS developed a contribution calendar in which each week got assigned to one specific partner. A weekly reminder was sent to each partner with some guidelines on how to create a PRECINCT post. In case the post was also shared on Twitter, it would be retweeted by the official PRECINCT page to enlarge its visibility (Figure 5-6).

Figure 5-6: Tweet from POLIS about PRECINCT event organized in May 2023.

5.6.3 Press Releases and broad Media Publications

In the early days of PRECINCT, a [press release](#) was published in February 2022 by VIAS communicating the purpose of the project (see annex II). In addition, VIAS established a press release planning with the LLs Leader (LL1 – ICS, LL2 – VIAS, LL3 – INLE and LL4 – ITL) in order to organise the communication activities around the initiation of the LLs operations.

In addition to the press releases provided by the LLs, the Consortium partners have also contributed to the notoriety and visibility of the project and have provided content at different stages of the project:

- Early stage – Launch of the project and general communication of its objectives.
- Middle stage – Living Labs Operation: the methodology implemented in the project, the stakeholders and end-users involved, the tools planned to be deployed and the societal objectives targeted.
- End of the project – Living Lab major findings and next steps identified to exploit and implement the PEP in the daily practices of the crisis management teams.

Three Living Labs also communicated a separate press release on the purpose of their work (Figures 5-7 to 5-9).

Table 5-9: Press Releases by the LLs and links

Press Releases by the LLs				
		Date	Name	URL
LL1	Ljubljana (Figure 5-7)	01/06/2022	press release	Link (UK) (SL)
LL2	Antwerp (Figure 5-8)	02/07/2022	press release	Link
LL4	Bologna (Figure 5-9)	19/01/2023	press release	Link
LL3	Athens	06/03/2023	Press release	Link

ICS / Current activities / Novice

Living Lab Operation Ljubljana was officially launched as part of the PRECINCT project

The PRECINCT project is a two-year project in which 40 international organizations participate and is financed by the European Commission. The project foresees 4 Living Labs (LL) and one of them was planned in Ljubljana. LL Operation Ljubljana officially launched at the beginning of June, which is the ninth month (M9) of the project.

01. June 2022

The goal of the PRECINCT project is to develop a platform for connecting different stakeholders of interdependent critical infrastructures (CI) and emergency services, and to look at possible cascading effects in the event of various unforeseen security events or planned disasters. The Institute for Corporate Security Studies (ICS Ljubljana) is the coordinator of the Slovenian part of the consortium.

The Ljubljana Living Lab (LL1) is a Multi-domain LL involving national rail and City bus transport, Electricity (DSO), Telecommunication infrastructure) and Municipality of Ljubljana stakeholders. The Thematic focus is a Multi-CI Coordination Center for major city Transport Hub.

LL1 Ecosystems

Figure 5-7: Press release LL1 Ljubljana (June 2022)

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Antwerpse politie wil wateroverlast beter voorspellen

Antwerpen - De Antwerpse politie werkt mee aan een Europees project om beter voorbereid te zijn op watersnood en de gevolgen daarvan. "In geval van een nakende overstroming, zouden de hulpdiensten zo vroeger kunnen starten met het nemen van gepaste maatregelen."

Zaterdag 2 juli 2022 om 11:18

Figure 5-8: Press Release LL2 Antwerp (July 2022) in "Gazet van Antwerpen"

Al via il progetto europeo PRECINCT per aumentare la sicurezza della rete di telecomunicazioni all'interno dell'Aeroporto di Bologna

Le cosiddette Critical Infrastructures (CI) europee sono sempre più a rischio a causa di attacchi informatici e fisici: terremoti, inondazioni e altri pericoli naturali si sommano ad attacchi umani. La ricerca si sta concentrando su soluzioni per proteggere le singole infrastrutture critiche, ma le interazioni tra esse sono diventate sempre più significative. In ambienti multioperatore la gestione è molto più complessa e deve necessariamente tenere conto di impatti ed effetti a cascata tipici del sistema di sistemi (e rete di reti), con grandi difficoltà a garantire la possibilità di una rapida ripresa. L'obiettivo del progetto PRECINCT, finanziato dal programma Horizon 2020 dell'Unione Europea, è quello di **mettere a sistema e connettere le parti che interagiscono all'interno della infrastruttura critica e quindi fornire una sicurezza informatica e fisica ("cyber-fisica") con un comune approccio che possa garantire protezione al territorio, ai cittadini e alle infrastrutture**. Un'area (PRECINCT) che possa essere replicata in modo efficiente per un'Europa più sicura.

PRECINCT prevede l'applicazione pratica delle soluzioni tecnologiche sviluppate in quattro "Living Labs": ad Anversa, Lubiana, Atene e Bologna.

Quello di Bologna ha come protagonista principale la rete di telecomunicazioni di Lepido all'interno dell'Aeroporto di Bologna, elemento essenziale per fronteggiare le emergenze ed aumentare la resilienza delle infrastrutture critiche, come appunto è l'aeroporto.

La rete di Lepido è il "collante" che mette in comunicazione tra loro i diversi attori della mobilità che operano nell'ambito del polo funzionale dell'Aeroporto, visto come hub multimodale, elemento essenziale per aumentare l'efficienza. **Impostazioni Cookie** inoltre coinvolti come stakeholders locali anche TPER e Marconi Express.

Figure 5-9. Press release LL2 Bologna (January 2023)

In addition to the press releases published by the Living Labs partners:

- VIAS (leader of WP5 LLS Operation and T5.4 LL2 Operation Antwerp) published an article in the magazine BlueConnect, the online knowledge point for the police, to present the project's societal objectives, the Digital Twin and Serious Games tools deployed in the LL2 Operation Antwerp, and how these tools will enhance the decision-making process and strategic actions of the CP-Ops members of the Antwerp city (Figure 5-10).
- ICS (leader of LL1 Operation Ljubljana) has published two more articles about the project, its objectives and the LL1 operation (Figure 5-11).

Those publications are also covered in section 5.6.4.

Figure 5-10: BlueConnect LinkedIn post - LL2 publication

Figure 5-11: ICS press release in the ICS newsletter – March 2023

5.6.4 Publications in the media

The PRECINCT project – or parts of it – was shared in a variety of scientific articles in magazines. Seven articles were written by the partners, the details of which are given in Table 5-10.

Table 5-10: media publications

Media publications					
Title	Authors	Title of magazine/website	Publisher	Date of publication	Link
Pred vrati so novi raziskovalnotehnoški projekti v okviru perspektive horizon 2020	Eva Čaleta	Korporativna varnost	ICS	26/09/2021	Link
Soluzioni Cyberphysical per le infrastrutture critiche, il progetto EU precinct e il living Lab Italiano	Fabio Fabbri	Key4biz	Supercom	03/11/2021	Link
PRECINCT	Lina Kolesnikova, Jenny Rainbird	ALERT	Institute of Civil Protection and Emergency Management	2022	Only available for members
Progetto Precinct avanti con la progettazione del Living Lab di Bologna	Redazione Key4biz	Key4biz	Supercom	26/06/2022	Link
TLC più sicure, all'aeroporto di Bologna parte il progetto Precinct. In campo Lepida.	Enzo Lima	CorCOM	ICT&Strategy, Gruppo Digital360	19/01/2023	Link
Aeroporto di Bologna, partito il progetto Precinct per la sicurezza "cyber fisica" della rete di telecomunicazione	Redazione Key4biz	Key4biz	Supercom	19/01/2023	Link

Media publications					
Title	Authors	Title of magazine/website	Publisher	Date of publication	Link
Politie Antwerpen test een Digital Twin en een Serious Game om de cascade-effecten van een overstroming te beheren en erop te anticiperen.	Shirley Delannoy, Isabel Verwee, Helen Witvrouwen	BlueConnect	BlueConnect	03/03/2023	Link
Povezovanje različnih kritičnih infrastruktur skozi projekt precinct	Aljoša Kandžič	Korporativna varnost	ICS	31/03/2023	Link
Resne igre	Peter Zidar	Življenje in tehnika	TZS	07/2023	Link

5.6.5 Flyers and brochures

One of the aims of WP6 is to increase the visibility of PRECINCT at third-party events. Two of the tools used to succeed in this mission were the PRECINCT brochure and flyer. The brochure touched upon the following elements:

- Goal of the project
- Technical objective
- PRECINCT concept
- Stakeholders
- Four Living Labs
- Key outputs
- Transferability Demonstrators
- Consortium
- Project team

The flyer provided a summary of the content of the brochure and only highlighted the project’s characteristics, objectives, impact and Consortium, as shown in Figure 5-12.

Figure 5-12: Flyer PRECINCT

5.6.6 Internal communications via Partners' channels

Updates on PRECINCT were also shared via internal communication channels of different partners, such as companies' newsletters and websites. In total, 22 internal communications were registered via the dissemination tracker, as given in Table 5-11.

Table 5-11: Internal communications

Internal communications					
Type of publication	Title	Authors	Link publication	Date of publication	Readership (estimation)
Article in newsletter	Precinct: un progetto per prevenire i rischi cyber e fiscali per le infrastrutture di rete critiche	LEPIDA	LINK		internal 600; external 11,000
Article	Precinct: coordinamento è resilienza	LEPIDA	LINK	30.04.2022	internal 600; external 11,000
Article - news on website	Precinct: coordination is resilience	LEPIDA	LINK	21.05.2023	internal 600; external 11,000
Article - news on website	Projekt PRECINCT	City of Ljubljana	LINK	20. 7.2022	Approx. 8,500 website visitors per day
Article in newsletter	PRECINCT: al via il Living Lab di Bologna	LEPIDA	LINK	30.10.2022	internal 600; external 11,000
Article on website	Politie wil impact op wateroverlast beter inschatten	PZA	LINK	30.06.2022	-
Article - news on website	ΣΥΓΧΡΗΜΑΤΟΔΟΤΟΥΜΕΝΑ ΠΡΟΓΡΑΜΜΑΤΑ ΑΠΟ ΕΕ	Athens International Airport (AIA)	LINK	-	-
Article - news on website	Συνεισφορά στην Αγορά	Attiki Odos (ATTD)	LINK	-	-
Article - news on website	Η Αττική Οδός επενδύει σταθερά στην έρευνα και την καινοτομία	Attiki Odos (ATTD)	LINK	-	-
Article in e-newspaper/website	Πώς θα είναι οι «έξυπνοι» συρμοί σε Μετρό Θεσσαλονίκης και Γραμμή 4 σε Αθήνα: Πώς θα επιταχυνθούν τα δρομολόγια	Ethnos.gr - Member of Open Digital Group	LINK	03.11.2022	-
Article in newsletter	Serious games e Digital Twin: presentati a Bruxelles i risultati del primo anno di PRECINCT	LEPIDA	LINK	30.11.2022	internal 600; external 11,000
Article in newsletter	PRECINCT - Opportunità di Standardizzazione	LEPIDA	LINK	30.12.2022	internal 600; external 11,000
Article in e-newspaper/website	Avviate le attività del Living Lab Operation Bologna per lo sviluppo del Digital Twin: PRECINCT	FS Technology	LINK	13.01.2021	-
Article - news on website	PRECINCT - Standardizations opportunities	LEPIDA	LINK	30.01.2023	internal 600; external 11,000

Internal communications					
Type of publication	Title	Authors	Link publication	Date of publication	Readership (estimation)
Article - news on website	Na poti k večji odpornosti kritične infrastrukture Mestne občine Ljubljana	City of Ljubljana	LINK	25.01.2023	Approx. 8,500 website visitors per day
Article - news on website	Obisk Gasilske brigade Ljubljana	City of Ljubljana	LINK	14.02.2023	Approx. 8,500 website visitors per day
Article - news on website	Wateroverlast in Antwerpen vòdr blijven met project Precinct	water-link ov	LINK	31.01.2023	/
Article - news on website	Predstavitev projekta	City of Ljubljana	LINK	05.05.2023	Approx. 8,500 website visitors per day
Article in newsletter	PRECINCT: presentate a Brussels le soluzioni sviluppate nell'ambito del progetto	LEPIDA	LINK	30.05.2023	internal 600; external 11,000
Article in newsletter	Standard dati generalizzati per infrastrutture critiche	LEPIDA	LINK	30.05.2023	internal 600; external 11,000
Article - news on website	Konferenca Precinct v Bruslju	City of Ljubljana	LINK	22.05.2023	Approx. 8,500 website visitors per day
Article - news on website	Sodelovali smo na osrednji konferenci s področja korporativne varnosti	City of Ljubljana	LINK	24.05.2023	Approx. 8,500 website visitors per day
Article in newsletter	Presentati a Bologna i risultati finali di PRECINCT	LEPIDA	not provided	30.09.2023	internal 600; external 11,000
Article in newsletter of Cluster Greentech	Aeroporto di Bologna progetto EU PRECINCT: sinergie degli operatori del territorio per migliorare l'accessibilità	Cluster Greentech	LINK	31.07.2023	500
Article - internal news site	Sodelovali bomo v EU projektu PRECINCT	Telekom	not provided	5.3.2021	2,500
Article - news on website	Predstavitev projekta Precinct na konferenci EUROCRIM 2023	City of Ljubljana	LINK	13.09.2023	Approx. 8,500 website visitors per day

Underneath in Figure 5-13, some of the internal communications achieved by the Consortium partners are illustrated:

(1) City of Ljubljana – Website communication

Moja Ljubljana > Evropska sredstva za Ljubljano > Projekt PRECINCT > Novice projekta PRECINCT > Obisk Gasilske brigade Ljubljana

torek, 14. 2. 2023

Obisk Gasilske brigade Ljubljana

Foto: arhiv

V ponedeljek, 13. februarja 2023, smo v okviru evropskega projekta PRECINCT organizirali obisk operativnega centra Gasilske brigade Ljubljana.

V sklopu EU projekta Precinct potekajo obiski operativnih centrov institucij oz. kritične infrastrukture (KI) vključene v projekt. V živem laboratoriju Ljubljana, ki bo omogočal testno okolje za inovacije projekta Precinct, sodelujejo Institut za korporativne varnostne študije – ICS, Mestna občina Ljubljana, Slovenske železnice, Prometni inštitut, Javno podjetje Ljubljanski potniški promet, Telekom Slovenije in Elektro Ljubljana. Namen obiskov operativnih centrov je podrobnejše spoznavanje posamezne institucije, njihovega načina delovanja ter medsebojno povezovanje z ostalimi deležniki, saj bomo sklopu živega laboratorija Ljubljana, med drugim, pripravili skupno platformo oz. skupni koordinacijski center, kamor bodo združeni podatki sodelujočih. Vloga skupnega koordinacijskega centra je pomembna, saj so informacije o stanju kritične infrastrukture ključne tako pri preventivnih aktivnostih, kot tudi pri posredovanju. V sklopu projekta pripravljamo tudi kopijo realnih podatkov v t. i. digitalnem dvojčku (digital twin) in scenarij kaskadnega dogodka, ki bo vključen v koncept resnih iger (serious games). Preigravanje scenarija kaskadnega dogodka bo omogočalo, da identificiramo svoje prednosti in slabosti pri odzivanju na dogodek. Na podlagi navedenega bomo lahko izboljšali svoje posredovanje in pripravili naš odziv v primeru, da do takšnega izrednega dogodka pride.

Tudi MOL upravlja s kritično infrastrukturo, ki bi jo lahko, posredno ali neposredno, ogrozile kibernetične fizične grožnje. Poleg upravljalcev kritične infrastrukture, ima Gasilska brigada Ljubljana ključno vlogo pri odzivanju v primeru kaskadnih dogodkov. Na Mestnem redarstvu, ki koordinira izvedbo projekta v MOL, smo se povezali z GBL, kjer so nas (člane slovenskega konzorcija in projektne skupine Precinct) prijazno sprejeli na strokovnem obisku, ki je potekal 13. 2. 2023. Poveljnik GBL je pripravil strokovno ter temeljito predstavitev delovanja GBL, Javne gasilske službe v Ljubljani ter odziva mesta v primeru izrednih dogodkov. Razprava je vključevala tudi zgoraj omenjene inovacije projekta Precinct. Dodano vrednost obiska je predstavljala detajlna predstavitev operativnega dela, pri čemer so nam prikazali proces sprejema klica, vozni park in tehniko s katero razpolaga GBL. Informacije pridobljene na obisku GBL bodo izjemno koristne pri nadaljnjih aktivnostih projekta Precinct.

Deli na:

Velika mestna družina

Turizem
Ljubljana

(2) Lepida – Newsletter

Newsletter #175 | maggio 2023

DIGITAL INNOVATION HUB EMILIA-ROMAGNA

PRECINCT: presentate a Brussels le soluzioni sviluppate nell'ambito del progetto

Si è tenuta nella seconda settimana di maggio la conferenza di PRECINCT, il progetto europeo rivolto al miglioramento della resilienza di Infrastrutture Critiche (CI). **Lepida** è partner del progetto nel Living Lab di Bologna (LL4) insieme ad Aeroporto di Bologna, Fondazione ITL e FS-Technologies, ma anche attore nodale con la propria infrastruttura di rete nell'ambito del sito sperimentale di Bologna. La conferenza è stata un'opportunità significativa per condividere e approfondire i temi più rilevanti per la protezione delle Infrastrutture Critiche (CI), la sicurezza cibernetica e la gestione delle emergenze, attraverso il confronto e l'apporto di gestori, esperti, industria e stakeholder.

Un intenso programma ha presentato le soluzioni sviluppate ad oggi nel progetto PRECINCT e i risultati di altri progetti europei correlati. Il filo conduttore è l'esigenza urgente di modelli e strumenti avanzati di supporto alla protezione di infrastrutture, impianti e servizi complessi tra loro interconnessi. L'innovazione gioca un ruolo importante, nonostante esistano barriere all'utilizzo da parte degli utenti finali. La formazione di tutti gli attori - dai decisori ai tecnici su procedure, strumenti e tecnologie dedicate - costituisce un fattore rilevante, ma il primo passo fondamentale per la resilienza è la cooperazione tra gestori di infrastrutture differenti ma interdipendenti per la condivisione delle conoscenze, in analogia a quanto in corso di sperimentazione nei Living Labs dei progetti. Da queste esperienze emerge chiara l'esigenza di infrastrutture di Big Data e standard in grado di abilitare lo scambio di informazioni e l'elaborazione di modelli previsionali per ridurre i disservizi e mitigare le situazioni emergenziali, garantendo la comunicazione in caso di crisi. Su queste tematiche specifiche **Lepida** ha apportato il proprio contributo nel panel della conferenza dedicato alle prospettive di standardizzazione di cui si parlerà in dettaglio nell'articolo seguente.

DIGITAL INNOVATION HUB EMILIA-ROMAGNA

Standard dati generalizzati per infrastrutture critiche

Come anticipato nel precedente articolo, durante la conferenza di Brussels si è svolto un Panel specifico sull'argomento delle prospettive di standardizzazione. Su questo argomento, già trattato al Workshop di PRECINCT di novembre, **Lepida** aveva delineato come opportunità la definizione dei percorsi dei dati di interscambio tra operatori di CI, strutturati cooperativamente per aumentare il livello di resilienza. In occasione dell'incontro di maggio la proposta è stata sviluppata ulteriormente: in particolare si è fatto riferimento ad una visione della International Telecommunication Union (ITU) che introduce la "metadattazione procedurale". In una visione di lungo termine, presentata nell'intervento, assieme ai metadati dei dati scambiati con le altre infrastrutture critiche, si ipotizza la presenza di una descrizione in termini funzionali delle azioni che una procedura intende svolgere sulle informazioni messe a disposizione da un altro operatore. Dati e procedure popolano un unico ambiente informatico, comune a tutti gli operatori: il flusso di elaborazione è definito sulla scorta dei dati disponibili, su come è possibile elaborarli, su quali sono le elaborazioni compatibili. Questo percorso può essere attivato in maniera non supervisionata al determinarsi di certe

condizioni di emergenza, prefigurando l'attivazione di Smart Contract tra operatori di CI. Una piattaforma collaborativa di dati e procedure così ideata risulterebbe facilmente scalabile, a bassi costi per nuovi operatori e un precursore di questo strumento potrebbe essere individuato nel progetto MargHERita dell'Emilia-Romagna, sul quale già si intende fare confluire i dati degli operatori del LL4.

4

lepida

Figure 5-13. Illustrations of communication organised by the partners Consortium

5.6.7 Videos

To maximize PRECINCT's visibility, EOS developed a short [video](#) on the mission of the project (Figure 5-14). The video is visually attractive, and the text was written without the use of a technical language. This helped to increase the likelihood of people sharing the video via social media and other platforms.

Figure 5-14: Illustration of the PRECINCT video made by EOS and showcasing the ambitions of the project

5.6.8 PRECINCT events & workshops

During the execution of the project, the PRECINCT Consortium organised two workshops and one event for both: the partners and other stakeholders.

The 1st Stakeholder Engagement Workshop (SEW) (Figure 5-15) was organized on May 5, 2022, and acted as the first PRECINCT event open to external participants. As the project had only started in September 2021, the first event was mainly focused on raising awareness of the project and its objectives, as well as presenting some initial findings and work. Additionally, this event was the first engagement that PRECINCT had with stakeholders. In total, the event was able to bring together 75 participants (out of 103) registered. During the event, except for one presentation by the EU-HYBNET project, PRECINCT partners presented the work being undertaken in each work package, the overall objective of each work package, and what the final vision of the project was.

The 2nd Stakeholder Engagement Workshop was held 6 months after the first on November 22, 2022, and co-organized with the PRAETORIAN project, a sister project of PRECINCT. This 2nd SEW aimed to build off the first and join the stakeholders of both projects to present how each project is approaching the same problem and update stakeholders on the PRECINCT work done since the last event. The event agenda also included working group sessions for the participants to further develop topics vital to the work of both projects (standardization & policy recommendations and PRECINCT & PRAETORIAN training and capacity building programmes) and a general session on exploitation. The participation in this SEW increased compared to the last from 75 to 109 signalling a positive trend that allowed PRECINCT to further reach stakeholders.

Figure 5-15: Picture 1st Stakeholder Engagement Workshop

The PRECINCT Conference took place on the 16th and 17th May 2023, and was organized with the participation of seven other H2020 & Horizon Europe projects, as follows:

- AI4CYBER
- EU-CIP
- EU-HYBNET
- PRAETORIAN
- DYNABIC
- STRATEGY and
- SUNRISE.

The goal of the conference was to bring together a large audience of CI stakeholders, including researchers, industry, civil society, policymakers, etc. It was also the first PRECINCT organized event in the second year of the project and allowed for partners to present an update on all the work that had been undertaken so far. To avoid duplication of the previous events, the Conference agenda focused on more high-level and cross-cutting issues such as countering hybrid threats, innovation uptake and EU legislation/directives on protecting critical infrastructure (e.g., CER & NIS2), while also providing certain follow-ups for certain PRECINCT outputs including the PRECINCT training and capacity building programme, the standardization and policy recommendation activities, and the living labs. Space was also given to the participating projects in the form of break-out sessions or short presentations on topics related to PRECINCT. This approach provided various benefits including a larger audience as stakeholders from the other projects, a wider scope for the discussion, and an exchange of ideas and approaches. As with the previous events, the PRECINCT Conference went well, with positive feedback and a large number of registrants. With this event, there was a KPI of 180 participants, and there were 177 registrations before the event with various in-person registrations the day of. Overall, a large number of different stakeholders involved, as shown in Figure 5-16. Even though a large portion of participants were PRECINCT partners, many other types of stakeholders also took part in the event. All the participants to this event are represented on Figure 5-17.

5. Please indicate what stakeholder group you belong to

[Plus de détails](#)

● Law Enforcement (Agency)	6
● First Responder	3
● Critical Infrastructure Protection...	12
● Critical Infrastructure Operator	27
● Industry and/or Technology Pro...	33
● Academia	27
● Student	3
● General Industry Consultant	20
● PRECINCT Partner	85

Figure 5-16: Stakeholders PRECINCT conference

Figure 5-17: PRECINCT conference

A final conference organized by EOS at M24 (September 2023) of the project aims to gather the project partners in one of the four Living Labs: Bologna (LL4). This event aims to showcase all open tools and assets of PRECINCT Ecosystem Platform to a broad CIs audience.

5.6.9 Trainings

Two major trainings were organised by T6.4 – PRECINCT Capacity Building Programme, led by TCNL. Those trainings took place at M12 and M20 of the project lifecycle:

- 2nd PRECINCT Stakeholders workshop organised in Brussels.
- PRECINCT event organised in Brussels.

These trainings aimed to incentivize discussion and dialogue in a direction that can influence accelerated adoption of PRECINCT’s concepts, innovation, blueprints and open tooling. The capacity building efforts aimed

to interface the CI community with the appropriate expertise, consultants, specialists within and outside the Consortium, such that industrial CI stakeholders, who are keen to exploit and integrate the project's advancements within their own organisations, have the right professional expertise to help and support responsible integration practices.

In addition, the 4 LLs organised dedicated trainings with their stakeholders and partners as a preamble of the interactive demonstrations sessions which took place in all the LLs to deploy the PRECINCT Ecosystem Platform components. Addressing specific content to the LLs stakeholders, those trainings aimed to train and inform the stakeholders/end-users and CI's operators to the PEP components, the reason why they were designed how they interact with the tools and how they had to be used. The details of these trainings are provided in D6.4 (M24).

5.6.9.1 Innovation session

In 2022, a training session was given by Inlecom Commercial Pathways on innovation training with a bias towards commercialization for critical infrastructure (Figure 5-18). The [recording of this training](#) was afterwards shared via social media channels and the website.

Figure 5-18: Innovation Training Session ICP

5.6.10 Physical and digital presence during events

The different partners of PRECINCT were encouraged to promote the project and their contribution at national and international conferences and workshops in order to inform others and increase the visibility. The partners were asked to update the dissemination tracker with their activities, and a total of 40 events were registered so far. The majority of events were conferences. Table 5-12 provides a snapshot of the conference participation.

Table 5-12: Conference participation

Conference Participation					
Name of Event	Organisers	Date	Location	Participating partner	Number of Attendees
UITP International Association of Public Transport - Security Committee meeting	UITP	10/06/2021	Online	ICP	30
PCSCI workshop at the ARES conference	ARES	17 – 20/08/2021	Online	ICP	340
16th International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security	SBA Research & University of Vienna, Austria	23 – 26/08/2021	Online	ICP	340

Conference Participation					
Name of Event	Organisers	Date	Location	Participating partner	Number of Attendees
CPS4CIP 2021	European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures (ECSCI)	08/10/2021	Online	ICP	15
Settimana della Bioarchitettura e Sostenibilità	AESS	17/10/2021	Online	ADB	65
CORTE Enforcement Working Group meeting	CORTE	01/12/2021	Brussels, Belgium & online	CORTE	
CORTE Enforcement Working Group meeting	CORTE	25/02/2022	Brussels, Belgium & online	CORTE	
EU-HYBNET Workshop	HYBNET	06/04/2022	Rome, Italy & online	AIT	65
2nd ECSCI Workshop	ECSCI	27- 29/04/2022	Online	KNT	50
ESReDA - 60th ESReDA Seminar on Advances in Modelling to Improve Network Resilience	ESReDA and University Grenoble Alpes	04 – 05/05/2022	Grenoble-France	AIT, UCD	35
Future Summits 2022	IMEC	17 – 18/05/2022	Antwerp, Belgium	IMEC	2000
ISCRAM	ISCRAM	22 – 25/05/2022	Tarbes, France	AIT	80
E-corridor Event	E-corridor (National Research Council Italy)	31/05/2022	Online	ADB	85
13th International Conference "Days of Corporate Security"	ICS	30/05 – 01/06/2022	Online	VIAS	
ISPIM Innovation Conference	ISPIM	08 – 08/06/2022	Copenhagen, Denmark	IMEC, VIAS	600
CORTE Enforcement Working Group meeting	CORTE	08/06/2022	Brussels, Belgium & online	CORTE	
International Cybersecurity Forum (FIC) 2022	FIC	07 – 09/06/2022	Lille, France	MON	10,500
14th International Conference on Applications of Statistics & Probability in Civil Engineering	Trinity College Dublin	09 – 13/06/2022	Dublin, Ireland	UCD + AIT + RDS	300
8th International Conference on Models and Technologies for Intelligent Transportation Systems	IEEE	14 – 16/06/2022	Nice, France	UCD + AIT + RDS	500
Projects to Policy	REA	30/06 – 01/07/2022	Brussels, Belgium	EOS	130
Cyber Consultations with Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine	EU Caber Direct	04 – 06/07/2022	Tbilisi, Greece	AIT	50
5th International Conference on Railway Technology: Research, Development and Maintenance	Elsevier	22 – 25/08/2022	Montpellier, France	UCD	500
PCSCI workshop at the ARES conference	ARES	23 – 25/08/2022	Vienne, Austria	AIT, ICP	25
6th Conference on Civil Engineering Research in Ireland (CERI 2022)	Trinity College Dublin & TU Dublin	25 – 26/08/2022	Dublin, Ireland	RDS	120
ESREL - European Safety and Reliability Conference	TU Dublin	28/08 – 01/09/2022	Dublin, Ireland	AIT + RDS + UCD	25
Open LL Day	IMEC	20 – 23/09/2022	Turin, Italy	IMEC	350
ESReDA - 61st ESReDA Seminar	ESReDA and Politecnico di Torino	22 – 23/09/2022	Turin, Italy	AIT	20

Conference Participation					
Name of Event	Organisers	Date	Location	Participating partner	Number of Attendees
CERISERIS1 FCT /INFRA INFRA2 ANNUAL EVENT	DG HOME	27 - 28/09/2022	Brussels, Belgium	UITP, CPT	
Cyber Consultation with the Western Balkan Partners	EU Cyber Direct	27 – 29/09/2022	Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina	AIT	40
TRA Lisbon 2022	TRA	14 – 17/11/2022	Lisbon, Portugal	ICP, VIAS, UITP	
CORTE Enforcement Working Group meeting	CORTE	17-18/11/2022	Brussels, Belgium & online		
8th International Conference SAMKB	SAKBM	05/12/2022	Belgrade, Serbia	ICS	100
8th ITS Hellas Conference “Transportation & Logistics 2022: Research – Reshape – Innovate”	ITS Hellas	07 - 08/12/2022	Athens, Greece	ATTD	100
1st Interoperability Event	STRATEGY Project	15/02/2023	Rome, Italy	EOS	45
14th International Conference "Days of Corporate Security"	ICS	22 – 23/05/2023	Brdo pri Kranju, Slovenia	AIT, TS, EL, ICS, LPP, SŽ, PI, MOL	
RISE-SD 2023	Satways	29 – 31/05/2023	Rhodes Greece	INLE	
RISE SD conference	SATWAYS	29 – 31/05/2023	Rhodes, Greece	KEMEA	
Barcelona 2023 Global Public Transport Summit	UITP	04 – 07/06/2023	Barcelona, Spain	ICP	100
CORTE Enforcement Working Group meeting	CORTE	14/06/2023	Brussels, Belgium & online	CORTE	
14th international conference on application of statistics and probability in civil engineering	ICASP	10 – 13/07/2023	Dublin, Ireland	RDS	400
Dnevi varstvoslovja - Days of Security Studies	Faculty of Criminal Justice and Security, University of Maribor, Slovenia	13. and 14/06/2023	Podčetrtek, Slovenia	MOL	
EUROCRIM	European Society of Criminology	06.-09.09.2023	Florence, Italy	MOL	
"EU-CIP Project & ECSCI Cluster 1st Annual Conference For Greater CI Resilience in Europe	ENG	20 – 21.09.2023	Brussels	ICP, KNT, ENG	
on Critical Infrastructure Resilience	ECSCI	05.12.2023	Online	ICP	
“Reinventing European resilience”	Trinity College Dublin	09 – 13.07.2023	Dublin, Ireland	AIT + RDS + UCD	
20-21 September 2023"	ADB / LEP / ITL / ENG	26.09.2023	Bologna Airport, Italy	ADB / LEP / ITL / ENG / Municipality of Bologna / University of Bologna / SRM / TPER / MEX / Laboratori Marconi	

Some examples of partner’s dissemination activities of PRECINCT are given in the following photos:

- Figure 5-19 – AIT’s LinkedIn post about PRECINCT during a presentation at the EU-HYBNET 2nd Annual Workshop

- Figure 5-20 – 14th International Conference "Days of Corporate Security" organized by ICS with PRECINCT Consortium partners (AIT, TS, EL, ICS, LPP, SŽ, PI, MOL)
- Figure 5-21 – PRECINCT partners at 14th International Conference "Days of Corporate Security".

Figure 5-19: AIT's LinkedIn post about PRECINCT at the EU-HYBNET 2nd Annual Workshop

Figure 5-20: PRECINCT partners at 14th International Conference "Days of Corporate Security"

Figure 5-21: 8th ITS Hellas Conference – ATTD partners presenting PRECINCT LL3

5.7 EU Communication guidelines

The Consortium had to ensure that in all communication activities related to PRECINCT, the visibility of the EU funding was guaranteed. This was ensured by:

- (1) displaying the PRECINCT logo.
- (2) displaying the EU emblem.
- (3) including the reference to the PRECINCT funding set out in the GA. For any communication activities, the following sentence is included: “The project has received funding from the European Union’s HORIZON 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101021668”.

The EU emblem and reference to EU funding (as shown in Figure 5-22) was displayed on all dissemination material in a way that is easily visible for the public and with sufficient prominence (taking also into account the nature of the activity or object).

Figure 5-22. Display of the EU emblem and reference to PRECINCT project and fundings provided

5.8 Expected impacts, measures and KPIs

Defined in the GA of the PRECINCT project, SMART KPIs were provided to monitor the communication activities achieved in T6.2. These KPIs are described in Table 5-13 with the actions required.

Table 5-13: Expected impacts, measures and KPIs

	Communication channels	Due month	KPI	Actions
Create a business-oriented image of the project and raise awareness of the benefits of the PRECINCT project within the targeted communities and the general public	Corporate identity	M1	Project design completed and templates available to partners M1	Development of the overall project design, templates, presentations, etc.
	Project website	M1-M24	PRECINCT website online – 500 unique visits/month expected by	Website creation and continuous updates
	Social media	M24	300 contacts in LinkedIn	LinkedIn and Twitter presence Guidelines communicated to the partners
		M24	200 followers in Twitter	
	Public communication materials	M5	1 project brochure	Creation of brochure; posters, white papers, footage/video
			1 poster/rollup per partner	
			1 white paper	
			2 project videos	
			4 scientific publications	Scientific publications by the partners
	Press Material	M24	5 press releases + 5 articles in magazines	Creation of press-releases templates, writing press releases and articles
Events	M7	PRECINCT Conference, society in general (local, regional and national institutions, entrepreneurs)	First Stakeholders workshop	
	M14	- Stakeholder workshops with CI operators and institutional stakeholders (2 workshops in Brussels M7 and M 14)	Second Stakeholders workshop	
	M18	1 major conference in Europe attended by at least 180 participants M18 including video recordings for keynote speakers	Self-organised: 1 major conference in Europe attended by at least 180 participants M18 including video recordings for keynote speakers	

6 Dissemination Plan and Activities

6.1 Dissemination Activities Objectives

In support of the communication activities, the dissemination strategy aimed to ensure public disclosure of the project results, both in professional language as in non-technical language, to the target groups such as academics and research institutes, CI operators, local and federal police services and local and federal administrations (justice and home departments, municipalities and other security and safety stakeholders).

The dissemination activities supported all six Work Packages (WPs) and were tailor-made in order to ensure maximum visibility, accessibility and impact of the project activities towards identified and targeted stakeholders. The main objectives of the dissemination activities of PRECINCT were to:

- 1) Target and inform specific audiences in the research community, selected industrial sectors, stakeholders, potential investors and future b2b customers.
- 2) Make the project outcomes available to the different target audiences and ensure transferability (e.g., through open-access publications).
- 3) Highlight PRECINCT benefits through its own distinctiveness.
- 4) Create long-term scientific influence.
- 5) Facilitate scientific reuse of the project results.
- 6) Receive inputs and feedback from various target groups.
- 7) Permit long-lasting commercial impact.

The dissemination activities were planned to run during the project, starting with the second phase of the project, and after the completion of the project with the dissemination of its results, findings and learnings by the Consortium partners activities.

6.2 Open access

The PRECINCT central goal was to ensure efficient dissemination and Communication activities during the project, support internal information sharing, all in line with a clear path to open access outputs in our transferability strategy which has EU CI stakeholders and interest groups as a principal target audience.

6.3 Dissemination players

PRECINCT included European (multiplier) organizations in order to maximize the impact of the project activities and results, including POLIS, EOS, UITP, CORTE, ITL, VIAS, ICS and PIL. In addition, the PRECINCT Advisory Board and other European organizations with whom a specific collaboration and liaison were established during the project contributed to communicating the project activities and disseminating the project results, thereby driving the exploitation of the PRECINCT outcomes. These additional connections included, but were not limited to, ECSO, Trust in Digital Life, DG Home, DG CNECT, and ENISA.

In addition, all members of the Consortium also partnered in executing the dissemination strategy and were, therefore, expected to play an active role. VIAS ensured that all Consortium partners contributed to dissemination activities in order to guarantee dissemination of the results.

6.4 Dissemination messages

The dissemination messages are highly dependent on the findings and learnings from the project's activities, and they mainly consisted of disseminating results of the projects. The key messages, as given in Table 6-1, were adjusted during the project life cycle, - to create the most relevant, valuable and specific outputs for targeted (groups of) stakeholders.

Table 6-1: Dissemination key messages

Working Package	Key messages
WP1	CIs Interdependencies network and the cascading effects network; Resilience aspects and Index; Interdependencies models; CIs protective measures; etc.
WP2	Blueprints
WP3	Serious Games training objectives and values Stakeholders and first responders' training needs
WP4	CIs Identification and Mapping, Early warning system detection, first responders needs. Digital Twin functionalities and Flood Models
WP5	Learnings from the LL methodology and its deployment in the 4 LLs; LL methodology best practices; Enhancement of Decision-making process thanks to the DT and SG; Improved response procedures; etc.
WP6	Open tools and assets platform

6.5 Target audience and its segmentation

Multiple stakeholders were identified for their role and interest in the project outputs. These stakeholders, and the level of decision-making processes they represented, were targeted by the dissemination activities and content throughout the project.

The following list identifies the stakeholders and their level of implementation:

- Local level:
 - Local Law Enforcement authorities
 - Local First Responders
 - Local Critical Infrastructure protection actors.
- National level:
 - National Law Enforcement authorities
 - National First Responders
 - National Critical Infrastructure protection actors
 - National agencies
 - National Ministries of Interior, National Ministries of Foreign and European Affairs.
- European level:
 - ENLETS: European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services
 - SENTER network: Network for Strengthening European Network Centres of Excellence in Cybercrime.
 - European Commission: DG Home (Directorate ISE: Industry, Synergies & enabler directorate/Directorate RTI:
 - Research, technology & Innovation directorate/ Corporate services Directorates), DG Connect (Directorate A: Strategy and General Affairs/ Directorate D: Security).

- Agencies/Bodies of the EC: European Defence Agency, The Computer Emergency Response Team for the EU institutions (CER-TU),
- The European Union Institute for Security Study (EUISS).

In addition, players from private/public domains were also targeted by the project findings and positive impact objectives. The Critical infrastructure operators were the main users of the technologies provided by PRECINCT and would benefit by early identification of potential cascading effects among different infrastructures. This would allow them to anticipate and take the necessary measures to avoid further damages or minimize the hazards due to physical and cyber-attacks.

Industry & technology providers (including SMEs) benefit from the PRECINCT developments in three ways:

- (i) direct relationships with Consortium members to perform complementary activities and technology transfer.
- (ii) potential agreements with industry players to maximize the exploitation and sustainability of the project results.
- (iii) the replication of the PRECINCT results in other European locations.

And finally, Academia & research institutes worked in collaboration with the first responders and CIs operators to identify the needs of the end-users and to get aligned with the market requirements. The collaboration also involved the technology providers to facilitate the technology transfer and awareness.

The different targeted stakeholders are schematized in the Figure 6-1.

Figure 6-1: PRECINCT Stakeholders - Communication activities

6.6 Dissemination Tools and channels

One sentence please to introduce this table.

Table 6-2: Dissemination tools and channels

Type of material	Activity	Channel
Publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific publications PRECINCT publications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Articles in scientific publications (e.g., peer-review journals) and blogs PRECINCT newsletters
Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Market showcase B2B networking
Online	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online disclosure of results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website Social media
Meetings & events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholders' engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feedback sessions Industrial events Training sessions Conferences Workshops
Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conferences proceedings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publication of proceedings

6.6.1 Online dissemination and interaction

The project results were disseminated on the PRECINCT website and promoted in the social media channels of both PRECINCT and its partners. All results will be available in English.

6.6.2 Academic, Scientific and Conferences Publications

The partners of the Consortium were encouraged to write scientific articles about their activities in PRECINCT and share these articles via social media and the dissemination tracker. So far, eight articles were written, as given in Table 6-3.

Table 6-3: Journal & conference papers

Journal/Conference papers							
Type of publication	Title	URL	Authors	Title of the Journal/Proceedings/Books series/Book (for book chapters)	Publisher	Year	Access
Paper	Risk Management with Multi-categorical Risk Assessment	Link	Sandra König, Stefan Schauer, Mona Soroudi, Ili Ko, Paraic Carroll	Advances in modelling to improve network resilience: Proceedings of the 60th ESReDA seminar	Publications Office of the European Union	2022	ISSN 1831-9424
Paper	Combining Cascading Effects Simulation and Resilience Management for Protecting CIs from Cyber-Physical Threats	Link	Sandra König, Lorcan Connolly, Stefan Schauer, Alan O'Connor,	Proceedings of the 32nd European Safety and Reliability Conference	Research Publishing	2022	doi:10.3850/978-981-18-5183-4_S20-03-343-cd

Journal/Conference papers							
Type of publication	Title	URL	Authors	Title of the Journal/Proceedings/Books series/Book (for book chapters)	Publisher	Year	Access
			Paraic Carroll and Daniel McCrum				
Consolidated proceedings	Cascading cyber-physical threats and effects Virtual Workshop, April 27–29, 2022	Link	Consolidated Proceedings of the Second ECSCI Workshop on Critical Infrastructure Protection and Resilience Virtual Workshop, April 27–29, 2022	Consolidated Proceedings of the Second ECSCI Workshop on Critical Infrastructure Protection and Resilience Virtual Workshop, April 27–29, 2022	Stienbeis	2023	ISBN 978-3-95663-285-3
Abstract	Security challenges in critical infrastructures in transport: the PRECINCT Athens use case	Link	Eftichia Georgiou, Ioannis Lymaxis	Research and Innovation Symposium for European SECURITY and Defence	RISESD2023	2023	/
Abstract	A Sustainable GIS-Based Serious Game Approach to Improve Railways Resilience	Link and link	M. Soroudi, M. Gordan, I. Ko, P. Carrol, D. McCrum, and F. Pilla	022, Fifth International Conference on Railway Technology	Academia.edu and	2022	DOI: 10.4203/cc.1.27.18
Abstract	S tehnološkimi rešitvami projekta Precinct do večje odpornosti kritične infrastrukture v Ljubljani	Link	Tinkara Bulovec, Roman Fortuna	Dnevi varstvoslovja 2023 - zbornik povzetkov	Univerza v Mariboru	2023	DOI: https://doi.org/10.18690/um.fv.4.2023
Paper (under review)	Coordination in serious games scenarios leveraging on dishomogeneous PSN	<i>Not provided</i>	C. Passerini, P. Zidar, T. Hadjina	<i>Not provided</i>	IEEE - PST Initiative	<i>Planned in 2023</i>	<i>Not provided</i>
Paper (under review)	Come supportiamo ora le infrastrutture critiche/data centre	<i>Not provided</i>	L. Simone, C. Passerini	<i>Not provided</i>	CLUST-ER INNOVATE	<i>Planned in 2023</i>	<i>Not provided</i>

In addition, four scientific articles are planned and are still under review at the time of finalising this deliverable. The publication of these articles is then not confirmed.

Table 6-4: Scientific papers

Scientific publication (peer reviewed)			
Planned Date	Description	Lead Contributor	Partners Contributors
Planned to be published in 2023	A review paper on "Critical Infrastructure Protection Blueprints: Challenges, Reference architectures and Deployment"	Djibrilla Amadou Kountche	UCD, AIT, RDS, BSC, VLTN, TNCL, LIST, ENG, MON, INLE
Planned to be published in 2023	A conference paper on "A Cybersecurity Ecosystem Platform for Critical Infrastructure Protection and its Description using OASIS TOSCA"	Djibrilla Amadou Kountche	LIST, ATTD, MON, KNT
Planned to be published in 2023	A Reviewed paper on "3C Information Model"	Cristiano Passerini	LEP
Planned to be published in 2023	Security challenges in critical infrastructures in transport: the PRECINCT Athens use case. In Springer book series: Security Informatics and Law Enforcement.	Ioannis Lymaxis, Eftichia Georgiou	INLE, KEMEA

6.6.3 Newsletters

Throughout the PRECINCT project, a total of eight newsletters were produced by the Consortium. A web page on the PRECINCT web site was dedicated to the newsletter collection (Figure 6-2). The aim of the newsletters was to give the stakeholders an update on the overall progress of the project and an insight into the different activities of the partners. Each edition contained approximately 10 contributions of 10 different partners. Figure 6-3 is an example of the newsletter concerning LL Athens. A contribution list and time schedule were developed to ensure a variety of topics and partners in each newsletter. The final version, approved by the Ethics Committee, was shared on the website³ and social media channels.

The objectives of the newsletters were to:

- Inform project partners and stakeholders of project news + updates.
- Provide information about relevant external events and resources.
- Disseminate key messages from Work Packages and activities.
- Ensure project partners and key stakeholders were up to date on projects achievements and impact.

In terms of actions:

- VIAS designed a template for the project newsletters and a planning identifying the partners contribution at M3.
- VIAS aimed at releasing a newsletter every three months.
- VIAS contacted the relevant partners for their input for the next newsletter.
- VIAS published the newsletters on the website and communicates about its release via the social media channels and the networks of the partners.

³ <https://www.precinct.info/en/publications/newsletters/>

Figure 6-2: Dedicated page on PRECINCT website for the newsletters and marketing tool

Living Lab Athens – Objectives and Transport Resilience overview

By John Limaxis, Technical Project Manager, Inlecom Commercial Pathways

Thematic focus: Increased resilience against cyber-physical incidents affecting urban transport

Key stakeholders: Athens International Airport, Attikéd Diadromes S.A, Attiko Metro S.A., KEMEA, coordinated by Inlecom

During PRECINCT 2nd Stakeholders Workshop Inlecom and KEMEA provided an overview of PRECINCT LL3- Athen's key objectives and activities so far. The presentation was kicked off by Inlecom, who is leading the coordination of PRECINCT LL3, by introducing the nature and expertise of LL3 Stakeholders and transport CIs. Following that, the Threat Scenarios developed by PRECINCT LL3 partners were introduced to the workshop's participants, along with the main challenges and problems identified by LL3 CIs operator in managing and mitigating such critical situations. Subsequently, the presentation focused on the implementation of PRECINCT project methodological framework and technological outputs by LL3. This included a presentation LL3 work for quantifying Athens Transportation Network Resilience Index and the vision for Athens Transportation network Knowledge Graph, aiming to ingest and interlink LL3 heterogeneous data and information for enabling CI's operators to respond faster or in automated ways.

Precinct Newsletter Issue 5 43

Figure 6-3: Newsletter PRECINCT

6.6.4 Physical interactive dissemination

The different partners of PRECINCT were encouraged to promote the project and their contribution at national and international conferences and workshops to increase the visibility. The partners had to regularly update the dissemination tracker with their activities, and a total of 40 events were registered so far and are highlighted in Section 5.6.10. Most events were conferences.

6.6.5 Additional dissemination channels

1. An external Advisory Board was composed at the beginning of the project, including other European organizations with direct relation with critical infrastructure to both get valuable input for the project in technical, social, environments, legal and economic terms, and to facilitate the dissemination of the project results by extending the PRECINCT community.
2. Liaison activities with related initiatives, specifically, projects from the SU-INFRA-01 topic, to establish collaborations to boost and maximize the communication and dissemination of the project results will be launched.
3. Outputs from PRECINCT will serve as a basis for guidelines for future UITP activities on security, including the development of the next UITP Policy Briefs and Position Papers, which have an impact at global level and in the operations of its working group on security.

4. PRECINCT will help bring new knowledge to the various activities interacting with the Security Commission, IT-ITS UITP Committees, Metro and Rail Commissions, Organising Authority Commission, UITP Training programme and Economics Committee to find synergies and to exchange knowledge on security.

6.7 Expected impacts, measures and KPIs

Specific KPIs have been associated with the Dissemination activities. Those KPIs and expected impacts are gathered in Table 6-5, with the actions required to achieve these objectives.

Table 6-5: Expected impacts, measures and KPIs (dissemination)

	Communication and Dissemination Channels	Due month	KPIs	Actions
Diss. and promote project activities among targeted stakeholders	Online marketing	M24	Social media posts: 2/week Twitter: 35 tweets LinkedIn: 43 posts	Website search engine optimization, continuously displaying the success of the project and community building, use of web analytics
	Newsletters	M1 - M24	Once every quarter	Regular publishing (+/- every 3 months) of a dedicated newsletter and contributions to external newsletters
	Press campaigns	M9 + M12	at least 5 press releases	Press releases in diverse media (radio, press, TV...)
	Conference presentations	M1 - M24	Data from logbook: at least 10	Participation in selected conferences
Liaison activities	Workshops and roundtables	M24	At least 4 events	Co-org. of workshops and roundtables

7 Conclusion

This deliverable presented PRECINCT's Dissemination, Networking and Communication Strategy implemented during the 24-month project duration. Its six sections defined the objectives, target groups, channels, means and indicators for successful research project communication, networking, and dissemination objectives.

Different communication channels were selected to efficiently address the different target groups and to reach a broad audience to ensure effective community building and to spread the results of the PRECINCT project. Collaboration with other initiatives such as ECSCI Consortium and PREATORIAN, DYNABIC, STRATEGY, EU-CIP, AI4CYBER, EU-HYBNET and SUNRISE projects contributed to achieve even more engagement with potential stakeholders. Partners' participation was also a key requirement to maximize the impact and visibility of the PRECINCT's achievements, solutions, impacts, and innovation.

The communication and dissemination activities followed the three phases of the project:

- Phase 1 included activities linked to project promotion of the project and were mostly produced during the first 6 months of the project.
- Phase 2 focused on the dissemination of the emerging findings and achievements. Direct stakeholder interaction is initiated. The interaction is carried out through meetings, events, and workshops.
- Phase 3 aimed to disseminate the project results effectively through scientific publications, policy briefs and events.

PRECINCT's social media strategy focused mainly on project promotion and dissemination and those activities took place mainly on Twitter and LinkedIn. PRECINCT's main social media channels are Twitter and LinkedIn, which are supported by YouTube. Exploitation of the project results is done through three domains: training, policy change and societal change.

8 References

[1] <https://ec.europa.eu/chafea/health/beneficiaries-corner/documents/factsheet-03.pdf>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 101021668

Annex I: KPIs monitoring and achievements

	Communication and dissemination channels	Due date	Total KPI	Actions	Progress towards KPI (last update at M24 – September 2023)
Create a business-oriented image of the project and raise awareness of the benefits of the PRECINCT project within the targeted communities and the general public	Corporate identity	M1	Project design completed and templates available to partners M1	Development of the overall project design, templates, presentations, etc.	M1
	Project website	M1-M24	PRECINCT website online – 500 unique visits/month expected	Website creation and continuous update	1650+ visits in 2 years
	Social media	M24	300 contacts in LinkedIn	LinkedIn and Twitter presence	392 followers
		M24	200 followers in Twitter		318 contacts
	Public dissemination materials	M5	1 project brochure	Creation of brochure; posters, white papers, footage/video	M4
			1 poster/rollup per partner		M4
			1 white paper		M24
			2 project videos		M8 + M14 + M20 + M21
			4 scientific publications	Scientific publications	4 (planned to be published in 2023)
	Press Material	M24	5 press releases + 5 articles in magazines	Creation of press-releases templates, writing press releases and articles	4 press releases organised by the LLs 5 press releases by partners in magazines
Events	M7	PRECINCT Conference, society in general (local, regional, and national institutions, entrepreneurs)	Stakeholders workshop in M7 (EOS)	M7	
	M14	- Stakeholder workshops with CI operators and institutional stakeholders (2 workshops in Brussels M7 and M 14)	Stakeholders workshop in M14 (EOS)	M14	
	M18	1 major conference in Europe attended by at least 180 participants M18 including video recordings for keynote speakers	Self-organised: 1 major conference in Europe attended by at least 180 participants M18 including video recordings for keynote speakers	M20	
Disseminate and promote project activities among targeted stakeholders	Online marketing	M24	Social media posts: 2/week	Website search engine optimization, continuously displaying the success of the project and community building, use of web analytics	Achieved at M24 <50 tweets in X (ex-Twitter) <50 posts on LinkedIn
			Twitter: 35 tweets		
			LinkedIn: 43 posts		
	Newsletters	M1 - M24	Once every quarter	Regular publishing (+/- every 3 months) of a dedicated newsletter and contributions to external newsletters	First newsletter published in 01.2022 Second newsletter published in 04.2022.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 101021668

	Communication and dissemination channels	Due date	Total KPI	Actions	Progress towards KPI (last update at M24 – September 2023)
					Third newsletter published in 07.2022. Fourth newsletter drafted in the period and published in 11.2022. Fifth newsletter published in 03.2023 Sixth newsletter published 06.2023 Seventh newsletter published in 09.2023
	Press campaigns	M9 + M12	at least 5 press releases	Press releases in diverse media; print, radio, press, TV...	2 press releases LL1 and LL2 2 are planned for LL3 and LL4
	Conference presentations	M1 - M24	Data from logbook: at least 10	Participation in selected conferences	47 conferences logged
Liaison activities	Workshops and roundtables	M24	At least 4 events	Co-org. of workshops and roundtable	EOS organises a workshop in Brussel on the 5 th of May 2022 (https://www.precinct.info/en/events-updates/events/events-organized-by-precinct-Consortium/)

Annex II: Living Labs Press releases

Press Release PRECINCT

4 of February 2022

Press Release

New HORIZON2020 project for a safer Europe

PRECINCT

Damage or destruction of critical infrastructures by natural disasters, terrorism and criminal activity can have devastating consequences for the security of the EU and the well-being of its citizens. Emerging threats, as well as unconventional attacks to critical infrastructures have exposed the limits of traditional risk assessment and risk mitigation efforts. Therefore, a common cyber-physical security management approach is urgently necessary. The new project PRECINCT strives to develop such an approach.

Safer infrastructures are a priority for the EU

Improving resilience of critical infrastructures has become a priority for the EU authorities. Consequently, a new EU Horizon 2020 project has been founded. The ambitious project PRECINCT "Preparedness and Resilience Enforcement for Critical INfrastructure Cascading Cyberphysical Threats" and effects with focus on district or regional protection has recently started.

PRECINCT aims to connect private and public CI (Critical Infrastructure) stakeholders in a geographical area to a common cyber-physical security management approach which will yield a protected territory for citizens and infrastructures. The ultimate ambition is that PRECINCT can be replicated efficiently and effectively for a safer Europe.

PRECINCT in numbers

CIs representing the transport, water, energy and ICT sectors and law enforcement agencies are actively involved in shaping the project development, which cover different types of CIs (private/public), size and geographical distribution. 4 Living Labs will be set up and the concepts will be further validated in 3 Demonstrators in the EU and beyond, more than 20 CIs and first responders, national authorities will participate creating a critical mass for adoption. This work will provide a robust evidence base of which approaches, and technical solutions are working, and which components provide clear advantages. Altogether, the consortium consists of 40 partners of excellence from 11 countries with very cross-cutting and complementary competencies.

For more information, please contact:
www.precinct.info/en/contact

The project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101021668

Annex III: Agenda PRECINCT EVENTS

1st Stakeholder Workshop

PRECINCT

Agenda

PRECINCT's 1ST Stakeholders Engagement Workshop

Maison des Associations Internationales, Rue Washington 40, 1050 Brussels
(On-Line, Zoom)

5th May 2022

08:30 – 09:00	<i>Welcome and Registration</i>	
09:00 – 09:10	Remarks	Jenny Rainbird, Project Coordinator (ICP)
09:10 – 09:25	Main Key Results and Roadmap	Gabriele Giunta (ENG)
09:25 – 09:50	BluePrints and Knowledge Graphs	Djibrilla Amadou-Kountche (AKKA), Stathis Zavvos (VLTN)
09:50 – 10:10	Serious Games	Daniel McCrum (UCD), Yash Shekhawat (NURO)
10:10 – 10:30	PRECINCT Architecture and Implementation	David Vermeir (IMEC)
10:30 – 10:45	Coffee Break	
10:45 – 11:00	PRECINCT Living Labs	Shirley Delannoy (VIAS)
11:00 – 11:15	Operation Athens	John Limaxis, Gerasimos Kouloumbis (ICP)
11:15 – 11:30	Operation Antwerp	Shirley Delannoy (VIAS)
11:30 – 11:45	Operation Ljubljana	Denis Čaleta (ICS)
11:45 – 12:00	Operation Bologna	Giuseppe Brancaccio (ITL)
12:00 – 12:40	Partners' feedback on the business requirements	Mark Bennett (ICP)
12:45 – 12:45	Morning Conclusion	
12:45 – 13:30	Lunch Break	
13:30 – 13:45	Critical Infrastructure Protection	Päivi Mattila (LAUREA)
13:45 – 15:15	PRECINCT's Future Technical Aspects	<i>Moderator:</i> Mark Miller (CPT) <i>Speakers:</i> Daniel McCrum (UCD), Stefan Lefever (IMEC), Stefan Schauer (AIT), Gabriele Giunta (ENG), Lorcan Connolly (RDS)
15:15 – 15:30	Coffee Break	
15:30 – 16:45	Drivers and Barriers for implementation of new CIP Solutions	<i>Moderator:</i> Mark Bennett (ICP) <i>Speakers:</i> Marisa Escalante Martinez (TCNL), Päivi Mattila (LAUREA), Vito Morreale (ENG), Benoit Baurens (AKKA), Denis Čaleta (ICS)
16:45 – 17:00	Conclusions	
		Jenny Rainbird, Project Coordinator (ICP)

2nd Stakeholder Workshop

PRECINCT's 2nd Stakeholder Engagement Workshop

AGENDA

Time	Topic	Room in the M.A.I
8:50 – 9:00	Welcome and Registration	Berlin Room
9:00 – 9:10	Opening of the Workshop	Berlin Room
9.10 – 9.30	PRECINCT: First Year Results & Highlight	Berlin Room
9.30 – 9.50	PRAETORIAN: First Year Results & Highlight	Berlin Room
9:50 – 10:40	Crisis Management: The Human Aspect of Critical Infrastructure Protection	Berlin Room
10:40 – 11:00	Coffee Break	
11:00 – 13.00	From Theory to Practice: Project Living Labs & Pilot Scenarios	Berlin Room
13.00 – 13.45	Lunch Break	
13.45 – 15.15	Working Group #1: Standardisation & Policy Recommendations	Paris Room
13.45 – 15.15	Working Group #2: PRECINCT Training & Capacity Building	Berlin Room
13.45 – 15.15	Working Group #3: PRAETORIAN Training & Capacity Building	Roma Room
15.15 – 15.30	Coffee Break	
15:30 – 16:00	Conclusions of the Working Groups	Berlin Room
16:00 – 17.00	Sui Generis Market: Business Requirements & Exploitation	Berlin Room
17.00 – 17.15	Conclusions & Closing of the Workshop	Berlin Room

PRECINCT Conference

PRECINCT

PRECINCT Conference
on
Critical Infrastructure Protection, Cybersecurity and Crisis Management

Day 1 – May 16th

AGENDA

<u>Time</u>	<u>Topic</u>	<u>Speaker</u>
9.00 – 9.30	Welcome and Registration	PRECINCT Consortium
9.30 – 10:00	Opening of the Conference	Ms. Natalja Miolato , <i>Project Advisor at the Research Executive Agency</i>
10:00 – 11:00	Protecting Critical Infrastructures facing Hybrid Threats	Chair: Dr. Stefan Schauer , <i>Senior Researcher for Security & Communication Technologies at AIT</i> Speakers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr. Päivi Mattila, <i>Director of Security Research Program & EU-HYBNET project coordinator</i> • Gilda de Marco, <i>R&D - European Projects at Insiel</i> • Rafa Company, <i>Valencia Port</i> • Edoardo Patelli, <i>University of Strathclyde</i>
11:00 – 11:15	Audience Q&A	Dr. Stefan Schauer , <i>Senior Researcher for Security & Communication Technologies at AIT</i>
<i>Coffee break</i>		
11.30 – 12.15	Panel Discussion on the Use of Living Labs	Chair: Mrs. Shirley Delannoy , <i>Researcher, VIAS Institute</i> Speaker: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thomas de Meester, <i>Innovation Specialist/Product Owner, IMEC</i>
12:15 – 12:30	Audience Q&A	Mrs. Shirley Delannoy , <i>Researcher, VIAS Institute</i>
<i>Lunch break</i>		
13:30 – 13.45	Practical Information on the Break-Out Sessions	Dr. Giovanni Nisato , <i>Managing Director & Founder of Innovation Horizons; Inecom Commercial Pathways</i>

13.45 – 15.15	Break-out session #1: Cybersecurity Datasets: Challenges and Opportunities	Dr. Erkuden Rios, <i>Director of Cybersecurity R&I projects at TECNALIA/Coordinator of AI4CYBER</i>
	Break-out session #2: Critical Infrastructure Resilience through Public Transport	Mrs. Carmela Canonico, <i>Safety & Security Manager at UITP</i>
	Break-out session #3: PRECINCT's 2nd Training & Capacity Building Programme	Mrs. Marisa Escalante, <i>Project Manager at TECNALIA</i>
<i>Coffee break</i>		
15.30 – 17.00	Break-out session #4: Standardization in PRECINCT & STRATEGY and future policy recommendations	Mrs. Loredana Mancini, <i>PRECINCT Impact Manager</i> Dr. Georgios Sakkas, <i>Research Associate at KEMEA</i>
	Break-out session #5: Validation of security tools for CI protection	Mr. Tim Stelkens-Kobsch, <i>Aviation Security Researcher at DLR,</i> Mrs. Eva Muñoz Navarro, <i>Project Manager at Grupo Etra</i>
	Break-out session #6: PRECINCT's 2nd Training & Capacity Building Programme	Mrs. Marisa Escalante, <i>Project Manager at TECNALIA</i>
17.00 – 17.30	Conclusions – End of Day 1	Dr. Giovanni Nisato, <i>Managing Director & Founder of Innovation Horizons; Inlecom Commercial Pathways</i>

Day 2 – May 17th

AGENDA

<u>Time</u>	<u>Topic</u>	<u>Partner Responsible</u>
8.30 – 9.00	Welcome and Registration	PRECINCT Consortium
9.00 – 9.15	Opening of Day 2	Dr. Giovanni Nisato, <i>Managing Director & Founder of Innovation Horizons; Inlecom Commercial Pathways</i>
9.15 – 9.30	Keynote speech	Mr. Giannis Skiadaresis, <i>Area Coordinator for Strengthened Security Research and Innovation (SSRI), DG HOME</i>
9:30 – 10.30	Panel Discussion on Innovation Uptake for Critical Infrastructure Protection	Chair: Mr. Mark Miller, <i>CEO of Conceptivity & Vice-Chair of EOS</i> Speakers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mr. Giannis Skiadaresis, <i>Area Coordinator for Strengthened Security Research and Innovation (SSRI), DG HOME</i>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr. Takis Katsoulakos <i>Managing Director for Inlecom Commercial Pathways (TBC)</i> • Mr. Isto Mattila <i>R&D Director at Laurea University of Applied Sciences & CEO of Dicitur Ltd</i> • Dr. Giovanni Nisato <i>Managing Director & Founder of Innovation Horizons; Inlecom Commercial Pathways</i>
10:30 – 10:45	Audience Q&A	Mr. Mark Miller , <i>CEO of Conceptivity & Vice-Chair of EOS</i>
<i>Coffee Break</i>		
10:45 – 11:45	The Resilience of Critical Entities: a New EC Directive	Chair: Dr. Georgios Sakkas , <i>Research Associate at KEMEA</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr. Erkuden Rios, <i>Director of Cybersecurity R&I projects at TECNALIA; Coordinator of AI4CYBER</i> • Dr. Aikaterini Poustourli, <i>Scientific Fellow of STRATEGY; Satways Ltd.)</i> • Mr. Paolo Venturoni, <i>CEO of the European Organisation for Security</i>
11:45 – 12:30	Resilience in Cybersecurity	Dr. Sandra Köniq , <i>Scientist/Researcher in Safety and Security at AIT</i>
12:30 – 13:00	After PRECINCT, DYNABIC	Dr. Erkuden Rios , <i>Director of Cybersecurity R&I projects at TECNALIA</i>
13:00 – 13.10	Closing of the Conference	Dr. Giovanni Nisato , <i>Managing Director & Founder of Innovation Horizons</i>

D6.2. Dissemination, Networking and Communication Strategy

PRECINT. WP6. T6.2. Partner Contributions. Social Media	WP	Task	Status	24-07-23	31-07-23	07-08-23	14-08-23	21-08-23	28-08-23	04-09-23	11-09-23	18-09-23	25-09-23	02-10-23	09-10-23
				Week 30	Week 31	Week 32	Week 33	Week 34	Week 35	Week 36	Week 37	Week 38	Week 39	Week 40	Week 41
Dissemination and Communication	WP6	T6.2	Running												
Social media publications	WP6	T6.2	Started												
Partners' planning															
AIT Austrian Institute															
AKKA HIGH TECH															
Antwerp Police Department															
Athens International Airport															
Attikes diadromes															
Attiko metro															
Barcelona Supercomputing															
Bologna Airport (ABD)															
CONCEPTIVITY															
CORTE															
DLR Dún Laoghaire- Rathdown															
ENG															
EOS															
ITL															
FSTechnology															
TNCL															
IMEC															
Inlecom Commercial Pathways															
Inlecom Innovation															
ICS															
KEMEA															
KONNECTA systems limited															
KU leuven															
LEPIDA															
Ljubljanski potniški promet															
LIST (Lux)															
Montimage															
Municipality of Ljubljana															
Nurogames															
POLIS															
Prometni institut Ljubljana															
Research Driven Solutions															
Slovenske železnice															
Telekom															
UITP															
University College Dublin															
Vias institute															
VLTN															
Water-link															

Annex V – Brand book Illustrations

Photography

The style and tone of the photos are real and bright.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 101021668

Examples

Powerpoint presentation

Protection zone

The protection zone is the blank space or margin surrounding the logo. It gives our logo breathing space for maximum visibility.

No other graphic or text should appear within the protection zone.

By determining a free space around the logo, we can guarantee that the logo will stand out.

The free space is determined by the size of the small circle. The width of this circle is the space that must be kept free around the logo.

This free space must be respected in case of use of the logo.

